

The image features a large, stylized logo for 'California Oughnut' centered horizontally. The logo consists of a white 'C' on the left, followed by the word 'CALIFORNIA' in white, uppercase letters, a white 'O' in the center, and the word 'OUGHNUT' in white, uppercase letters on the right. The background is split into two main sections: the left side shows a teal-tinted image of palm trees against a light sky, and the right side shows an orange-tinted image of a city skyline at sunset. Two large, semi-transparent circles overlap the center of the image, one teal and one orange, framing the logo.

CALIFORNIA OUGHNUT

A SNAPSHOT
AND REPORT ON
CALIFORNIA'S SOCIAL
AND ECOLOGICAL
PERFORMANCE

NOVEMBER 2025

The Doughnut Economics framework provides a concise visual assessment of an economy's performance based on social and ecological indicators.

We hope the California Doughnut can serve as a compass to help orient us towards meeting the needs of all people within the limits of the planet. By compiling social and ecological indicators, this report provides a snapshot of California's progress towards meeting this goal. It also provides deep-dive insight behind each indicator, including policy and justice considerations. The aims of this report are to:

MEASURE

California's current ecological overshoot and social shortfall

REFRAME

California's economic performance to align with social and ecological goals

INSPIRE

wider adoption of this framework within local governments, educational institutions, and community organizations

INVITATION TO COLLABORATE

We have done our best to connect with a wide range of stakeholders and experts around the state, however we acknowledge that these indicators are not perfect and invite feedback. We consider this a living document and hope others will join in updating the California Doughnut.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This report was produced by the California Doughnut Economics Coalition (CalDEC). It was co-authored by Alaitz Aritza (lead on the snapshot), Julian Kraus-Polk (lead on the report), Franziska Raedeker, John Lydon, Jamie Chesbrough, and Stephanie Luz Cordel. Many CalDEC employees and volunteers offered guidance and support throughout, notably Brian Dowling, along with Anne Sheridan, and Aaron Blanco. Huge thank you to all our partners from academia, government, and civil society, and to Ben and Giles for designing the report. This report was partly funded by the Cisco Foundation.

CALIFORNIA DOUGHNUT ECONOMICS COALITION

The California Doughnut Economics Coalition is a worker self-directed nonprofit organization, working for a California where people and the planet can thrive together. CalDEC seeks to create a new economic narrative for California, focused on social wellbeing and ecological health. Our work is organized into three pillars: 1) connect and strengthen ongoing state policy initiatives; 2) provide support for cities to use the Doughnut framework; and 3) facilitate education and curriculum development on Doughnut Economics. This California Doughnut Snapshot - assessing the overall social and ecological performance of the state - provides the foundation for our work ahead.

Learn more at caldec.org

THE CALIFORNIA CONTEXT

California is the United States' 3rd largest state by land mass and has its largest population, with over 39 million residents.¹

If considered as an independent nation, California would be the world's 4th largest economy.² California is considered a biodiversity hotspot due to a high concentration of endemic plants and animals.³

Even as one of the richest states,⁴ California has problems meeting the needs of all its people and maintaining a healthy environment.^{5,6}

Inequality has left many Californians unable to afford basic necessities like housing, food, education, and medical care.⁷

Meanwhile, a society built around excessive consumption and private transportation has led to a host of environmental ailments, including climate change, biodiversity loss, and freshwater scarcity.^{8,3,9}

How can we begin to solve these intersecting social and ecological crises if we prioritize growing our economy over improving wellbeing and safeguarding our shared home? This is where Doughnut Economics comes in.

LAND ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We acknowledge that the land now known as California has been stewarded by Indigenous peoples since time immemorial. Their centuries of wisdom demonstrate that thriving within ecological boundaries is not a new concept but a longstanding practice. As we embrace the principles of Doughnut Economics - balancing human needs with planetary health - we commit to learning from and uplifting Indigenous people and their knowledge to build a regenerative and equitable future for all. To deepen your understanding of and engagement with Native peoples, check out Redbud Resource Group's [*Going Beyond Land Acknowledgements workshops*](#).

INTRODUCING DOUGHNUT ECONOMICS

Doughnut Economics is a way to determine whether an economy is meeting the basic needs of its people within the means of the planet.

Conceived by economist Kate Raworth in 2012, Doughnut Economics is influenced by various economic fields, in particular the work of Ecological Economics, to re-embed the economy within our social and biophysical systems.¹¹

Since then, Doughnut Economics has been widely adopted. It has been used to compare social and ecological performance between nations,¹² and it is increasingly being used as a framework for local and regional decision making.¹³

Currently, no country is operating within the Doughnut's safe and just space, where basic needs are met without environmental pressures exceeding planetary boundaries.¹²

Wealthier countries tend to meet minimum social thresholds, but severely overshoot ecological boundaries, while poorer countries tend to be below social thresholds, yet do little to contribute to planetary overshoot.¹⁴

Satisfying the needs of all people within the limits of the planet is the crucial issue of our time and the fundamental goal of Doughnut Economics.

LEARN MORE
at the Doughnut
Economics Action Lab,
doughnuteconomics.org

THE OUTER DOUGHNUT

Measures environmental health. It has 9 categories based on the Stockholm Resilience Centre's Planetary Boundaries.¹⁵

Overshooting the ecological ceiling risks destabilizing the earth systems which humans rely on.

THE INNER DOUGHNUT

Measures social well-being. It has 12 categories, based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).¹⁶

Falling short of the social foundation means some people are lacking basic essentials like healthy food, clean water, and housing.

THE SAFE AND JUST SPACE

This is where all life can thrive. The more indicators sit within the inner and outer boundaries of the doughnut, the better an economy is at satisfying the needs of its people within the limits of the planet.

DEVELOPING THE DOUGHNUT

Photo Credit: Mos Sukjaroenkraisri on Unsplash

DEVELOPING THE DOUGHNUT

The California Doughnut is comprised of data from a variety of sources and validated by multiple stakeholders.

Our process started with an extensive review of previous Doughnut research alongside data on current social and ecological conditions in the state of California.

In total, we investigated well over 200 indicators and selected around 100 as potential fits for 21 categories generally included in Doughnut assessments.

We collaborated with experts from the Doughnut Economics Action Lab as well as regional experts within various local academic, governmental, and nongovernmental organizations to narrow and improve this list. Each domain utilizes two representative indicators to assess the social and ecological conditions in each category. The social foundation is made up of 24 indicators divided into 12 categories, while the ecological ceiling consists of 18 indicators divided into 9 categories.

While most of our indicators are similar to those found in other Doughnut reports, there were several instances where we included previously unused indicators that stand out as especially important given the context of California.

Around 50% of the indicators are documented by government agencies, 30% by NGO reports, and 20% by academic reports and peer-reviewed articles.

Averages are used throughout the report for a more concise understanding, not necessarily for mathematical precision, particularly with combined averages.

THE CALIFORNIA DOUGHNUT

Provides us an overview of California's social and ecological performance.

California is overshooting most ecological indicators and falling short on all social indicators.

WATER & SANITATION is our **best-performing** social category but still needs improvement

PEACE & JUSTICE is our **worst-performing** social category

OZONE DEPLETION is the only ecological category not in overshoot

CLIMATE CHANGE is our **worst-performing** ecological category

SOCIAL FOUNDATION

This page provides a breakdown of each social category into two representative indicators.

- WATER & SANITATION**
 - Water Quality
 - Sanitation Access
- ENERGY**
 - Energy Burden
 - Energy Reliability
- CONNECTIVITY & TRANSPORTATION**
 - Internet Access
 - Transit Report Card
- HOUSING**
 - Homelessness
 - Housing Burden
- EQUITY**
 - Gender Pay Gap
 - Racial Equity Index
- SOCIAL COHESION**
 - Income Inequality
 - Report Not Happy

- FOOD**
 - Food Insecurity
 - Vegetables Per Day
- HEALTH**
 - Life Expectancy
 - Healthcare Affordability
- EDUCATION**
 - Literacy Rate
 - Student Loan Debt
- INCOME & WORK**
 - Poverty
 - Unemployment
- PEACE & JUSTICE**
 - Violent Crime
 - Police Scorecard
- POLITICAL VOICE**
 - Voter Turnout
 - Registered Voters

SOCIAL FOUNDATION

If we unroll the Doughnut, we can get a better understanding of what information is captured by each social indicator. This visualization also allows us to see the extent of California's shortfall in each area.

THE SAFE AND JUST SPACE FOR HUMANITY

ECOLOGICAL CEILING

This page provides a breakdown of each ecological category into two representative indicators.

NITROGEN & PHOSPHORUS

- Eutrophication Potential
- Nitrogen Leached

OZONE DEPLETION

- Ozone-Depleting Substances
- Ozone Layer

BIODIVERSITY LOSS

- Unprotected Area
- At-Risk Species

LAND-USE CHANGE

- Forest Cover
- Ecological Footprint

FRESHWATER USE

- Ground Water
- Water Footprint

CLIMATE CHANGE

- Greenhouse Gas Emissions
- Non-Renewable Electricity

OCEAN ACIDIFICATION

- Ocean pH
- SO₂-Eq Footprint

CHEMICAL POLLUTION

- Landfill
- Toxic Releases

AIR POLLUTION

- O₃ Pollution
- Particulate Matter

ECOLOGICAL CEILING

If we unroll the Doughnut, we can get a better understanding of what information is captured by each ecological indicator. This visualization also allows us to see the extent of California's overshoot in each area.

EQUITY CONSIDERATIONS

As we examine the social, ecological, and economic challenges facing California, it is crucial to recognize that these issues do not impact all communities equally.

Systemic inequities have resulted in disproportionate burdens on historically marginalized and underserved populations, with some individuals facing compounded challenges due to intersecting identities, such as being both low-income and a person of color, or identifying as LGBTQ+ while living with a disability.

LOW-INCOME COMMUNITIES

Individuals and families in low-income areas are disproportionately affected by food deserts, housing unaffordability, and limited job opportunities. These economic constraints often force low-income households to live in areas with poor air and water quality, exacerbating health risks.¹⁷

WOMEN

Women, particularly single mothers and caregivers, are at higher risk of housing instability, economic hardship, and food insecurity. During climate crises, women are also more vulnerable to safety risks and violence.¹⁸

PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

Individuals with disabilities encounter significant barriers during climate emergencies due to inaccessible infrastructure and services, such as shelters or evacuation routes. In addition, systemic unemployment rates for people with disabilities remain higher than for the general population, contributing to increased housing insecurity and economic stress.¹⁹

IMMIGRANTS AND REFUGEES

California's immigrant and refugee populations often live in overcrowded or substandard housing and face language and systemic barriers when accessing social services, including food assistance and unemployment benefits. Furthermore, they are more likely to reside in climate-vulnerable areas, such as floodplains or industrial zones.²⁰

BLACK, INDIGENOUS, & PEOPLE OF COLOR (BIPOC)

In California, BIPOC communities frequently reside in areas with higher pollution levels and greater exposure to environmental hazards due to systemic social inequities. These communities also face higher rates of housing instability, unemployment, and food insecurity compared to white populations.²¹

LGBTQ+ INDIVIDUALS

Facing social discrimination, LGBTQ+ individuals in California often have less access to safe housing, healthcare, and employment opportunities, which are further exacerbated during climate events and economic downturns. Homelessness is disproportionately high among LGBTQ+ youth, with many lacking stable and supportive environments.²²

RELIGIOUS MINORITIES

Religious minorities often encounter prejudice and systemic inequities that limit their access to social safety nets, including housing and unemployment services. These inequities are exacerbated during disasters, as resources are often distributed unequally.²³

RURAL COMMUNITIES

Rural areas in California lack the infrastructure and resources necessary to combat social issues like unemployment, food insecurity, and limited access to affordable housing. These deficits also increase vulnerability to climate and social challenges.²⁴

WHAT YOU CAN DO

STATE POLICYMAKERS

Use this information to inform policies that improve well-being while reducing California's environmental impact.

CITY LEADERS

Adopt Doughnut Economics at a local level, helping build a better economy from the ground up.

EDUCATORS

Teach the concept of Doughnut Economics in your curriculum, creating a broader understanding of socioecological systems. You can find more resources to help **here**.

COMMUNITY

Demand better from our policymakers by introducing them to the idea of Doughnut Economics

RESEARCHERS

Help improve the indicators and data for measuring social and ecological performance for the state, regions, and cities in California.

LEARN MORE ABOUT HOW YOU CAN COLLABORATE BY VISITING THE CALIFORNIA DOUGHNUT ECONOMICS COALITION AT [CALDEC.ORG](https://caldec.org)

DEEP DIVING INTO THE DATA

HOW TO READ THESE PAGES

DATA SNAPSHOT
DEEP DIVING INTO THE DATA

CLIMATE CHANGE

Human activity releases greenhouse gases, mainly by burning fossil fuels and degrading the environment.

An increased concentration of these gases in the atmosphere leads to climate change. In California, the main sectors producing emissions include transportation, industrial processes and manufacturing, agriculture and land-use change, electricity generation, heating and cooking, and the production and disposal of refrigerants.

The biosphere has a certain capacity to absorb greenhouse gases, but if we exceed this limit, we risk damaging Earth's life support systems, which we rely on to survive.?

CLIMATE CHANGE

- CONNECTIVITY & TRANSPORT
- EDUCATION
- ENERGY
- EQUITY
- FOOD
- HEALTH
- HOUSING
- INCOME & WORK
- PEACE & JUSTICE
- POLITICAL VOICE
- SOCIAL COHESION
- WATER & SANITATION

ECOLOGICAL CEILING

- AIR POLLUTION
- BIODIVERSITY LOSS
- CHEMICAL POLLUTION
- CLIMATE CHANGE
- FRESHWATER USE
- LAND-USE CHANGE
- NITROGEN & PHOSPHORUS
- OCEAN ACIDIFICATION
- OZONE DEPLETION

DATA DETAILS
SOURCE

The pages in this section provide more detail and context on the chosen ecological ceiling or social foundation.

The first page explains the category in more detail, providing the reader a better understanding of its importance and relevance to the California Doughnut.

Interactive table of contents lets you jump to specific categories and supporting material.

Performance provides the headline numbers for California's performance in each category. Numbers are rounded. For precise numbers, see the complete data spreadsheet [here](#).

Policy spotlight summarizes government policies that have the most power to affect this category.

Justice spotlight looks at whether and how demographic groups are impacted differently by the category.

Maps or charts with geographic or visual data for the given category are included where available.

CLIMATE CHANGE

PERFORMANCE

1,890% 62%

Overshoot in GHG per capita Overshoot in electricity from non-renewable sources

WHAT WE MEASURED

Greenhouse gas footprint

- Currently, global average per capita emissions are between 4-5 tonnes. The average American emits around 15 tonnes per year from a territorial perspective and around 23 tonnes per year from a consumption-based perspective.³ In some countries, per capita emissions are below 1 tonne per capita.⁴
- According to the Environmental Protection Agency, consumption-based CO2 equivalent emissions in California were 19.6 tonnes per capita in 2020.⁵ The emission inventory from the California Air Resources Board estimates territorial emissions in California to be around 10 tonnes per capita.⁶
- Territorial inventories do not include categories like international air travel and imported food, goods, and services.

RENEWABLE ENERGY

- Apart from reducing energy consumption, another way to reduce our greenhouse gas footprint is to switch from fossil fuels to renewables like wind, solar, and geothermal. Electricity generation accounts for around one third of total energy use.⁷ We chose not to include nuclear, biomass, or hydropower due to their environmental impacts, even if they are playing a role as transitional energy sources.

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- The **Global Warming Solutions Act of 2006 (AB 32)** and **California Climate Crisis Act of 2022** set a goal of 259 MMT CO2 eq per year by 2030 and 64.6 MMT CO2 eq by 2045. This is equal to around 7 tonnes 2030 and 1.7 tonnes per capita in 2045.⁸
- The **SB 100 (2018) California Renewables Standard Program** requires that renewable 100 percent of California's electric retail sales. This includes sources like nuclear, biomass

What we measured explains how the given category is measured and the data sets for the indicators.

CLIMATE CHANGE

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- While some Californians have carbon footprints below the state average, wealthy individuals emit 50+ tonnes per year.¹¹ In the accompanying map, you can see household emissions for different census tracts in the Bay Area.^{12,13}
- Around half the people on Earth do not exceed the per capita limit for CO2 emissions. Inequality in emission profiles mirrors the inequality of access to wealth and resources both within and between countries.¹⁴
- In general, countries and locations with the least emissions will be hardest hit by the impacts of climate change. Burning greenhouse gases also produces wealth, so these countries tend to have the least wealth reserves to invest in resilience and recovery from climate impacts.^{14,15}

Map: Carbon footprint of San Francisco Bay Area households by Census block groups.¹²

SOCIAL FOUNDATION

DATA SNAPSHOT

DEEP DIVING INTO THE DATA

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- POLITICAL VOICE
- SOCIAL COHESION
- WATER & SANITATION

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CONNECTIVITY & TRANSPORT

Connectivity to the digitized world is of increasing importance in society.

Digital connection provides people with vital access to information, services, opportunities, communication options, and social networks. Out of 36 OECD countries, the USA ranks 31st for internet access among households.⁴ Despite California being home to some of the most advanced technologies, many households still lack access to the internet.¹ California is ranked 7th in the country for access to wired or fixed wireless broadband.³

Likewise, access to mobility and transportation is essential for economic, social, and political activities. As one of the largest states by area, transportation is essential for Californians to thrive. The state has significant room for improvement to both increase the accessibility and sustainability of its transit systems.² A 2021 mode-share study analyzing data from 2012-2017 found that biking, walking, and public transportation were all declining, contradicting California's goals to increase public and active transit.⁵ The study also revealed that by far the most dominant mode of transportation in the state is private vehicles, with approximately 80% of the total transit share.⁵

Overall, California experiences a moderate to significant shortfall in providing Californians with adequate access to connectivity and transportation.

Despite California being home to some of the most advanced technologies, many households still lack access to the internet.¹

DATA SNAPSHOT

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CONNECTIVITY & TRANSPORT

SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

17%

 Shortfall in households with broadband internet subscription

40%

 Shortfall in transit report card score (vehicle miles traveled, transit access)

WHAT WE MEASURED

Connectivity

- Under-connected households are found by adding the percentage of households “without an internet subscription” and households on a “cellular data plan with no other type of internet subscription”. In 2023, this included 5.7% and 11.2% of California households, respectively, for a total of 16.9%.¹ Other metrics of connectivity, such as “meaningful internet access”, go beyond internet subscription alone to include aspects like digital literacy skills, finding that 30% of Californians are lacking in this regard.⁶

Transport

- We utilized two of the metrics from the Transit Report Card developed by Transportation for America: vehicle miles traveled (VMT), and transit access.² VMT measures the total miles driven by all vehicles on a given state’s roadways in a given year to better understand transit ridership. Each state’s VMT per capita was assigned a score from 1-5, with a 1 reflecting more driving—and

likely less transit usage—and a 5 reflecting less driving and more transit usage.^A Transit access measures the number of jobs you could reach with a 45-minute transit ride compared to a 45-minute drive, and how well transit access was distributed across the state. We decided to use just these two measures in order to pinpoint performance on sustainability and access-related elements of the transit system in California. For VMT, California received a 4 out of 5, with 8,626 vehicle miles traveled per capita in 2019.^B For transit access, California received 2 out of 5, based on criteria described above. Overall, California received a combined score of 6 out of the 10 points possible.²

- A secondary indicator often used to measure transit sustainability and car dependency is the share of different modes of transportation. A study from the National Center for Sustainable Transportation analyzing data from 2012-2017 found that California is not on track to meet its goal to decrease car dependency and increase public and active transportation.⁵ Regional metropolitan planning organizations in California produce more recent and regular data on the transit modal split, which might be utilized for future assessments.
- We also considered using an indicator to measure walking-distance to public transportation. However, straight-line Euclidean distance methodology is no longer used due to flaws in data related to urban obstacles, such as freeways, in California's built environment.⁸

A. Scoring system from 1-5, with a 1 reflecting more driving—and likely less transit usage—and a 5 reflecting less driving and more transit usage

- Greater than 14,000 VMT per person
- 11,500 – 14,000 VMT per person
- 10,000 – 11,500 VMT per person
- 8,500 – 10,000 VMT per person
- Less than 8,500 VMT per person

B. See more recent data and trends on vehicle miles traveled (VMT) from [Caltrans](#). California has lower per-capita VMT than the U.S. average, but is still far from its stated climate goal and is trending in the wrong direction.

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DATA DETAILS

SOURCES

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CONNECTIVITY & TRANSPORT

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- California recently secured a \$70 million grant from the federal State Digital Equity Capacity Grant Program to address digital equity.^{9,10}
- [Senate Bill 156](#) provides \$6 billion to improve infrastructure to expand broadband access to businesses and homes.¹¹
- 2024 saw many transportation policies under consideration or signed into law, including expanded service area and fare discounts for seniors in Sacramento ([AB 1924](#) and [AB 263](#)), and improving roadway design for pedestrians, cyclists, and transit users to meet Caltrans requirements ([SB 960](#)).^{12,13,14,15}

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Rural and low-income households are less likely to have broadband access than their counterparts.¹⁶
- As people age, their ability to independently transport themselves declines and they become reliant on relatives and public transit options.¹⁷
- Rural households lack access to public transit links, medical transportation services, and car sharing opportunities.¹⁸

Figure: Broadband adoption in California.⁷

DATA SNAPSHOT

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EDUCATION

Education is essential for all Californians to be able to fruitfully engage with their communities and create a thriving society.

Quality education also provides people with the skills necessary to participate in the workplace and be involved in the democratic process. California holds one of the worst literacy rates in the United States, ranking 49th out of all states in 2020.³

In addition, pursuing higher education in the United States often requires taking on significant debt. This places a financial burden on millions of Californians who pursue further studies. The steep cost of education is a factor in people delaying other life goals such as marriage, starting families, and home ownership.⁴ California uses a combination of federal, state, and institutional funding schemes to lower tuition costs.⁵ However, high non-tuition costs, such as housing, can deter attendance, increase inequities, and lead to significant financial burden on students who do pursue higher education.⁵ 3.8 million Californians still owe a combined total of over \$142 billion in student loan debt.⁶

Overall, California experiences a significant shortfall in providing Californians with a sufficient level of education.

California holds one of the worst literacy rates in the United States, ranking 49th out of all states in 2020.³

DATA SNAPSHOT

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EDUCATION

SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

28%

Shortfall in literacy proficiency

46%

Shortfall based on college graduates with student loan debt

WHAT WE MEASURED

Literacy Rate

- Literacy rate is measured by the Program for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies (PIAAC), which assesses literacy, numeracy, and problem solving skills among the adult population. At Literacy Level 1 (on a 0-5 scale), people are able to locate information in text, find relevant website links, identify relevant text when information is cued, and the ability to understand the meaning of short texts and organization of lists on a page. PIAAC is a strong assessment of California's education system because it measures essential skills, including literacy, needed for workforce success and daily life.⁷ Based on data from 2012-2017, 28% of Californians aged 16-74 are at or below Literacy Level 1.¹ However, many California residents attended school in other states or countries before moving to the state, so this is not necessarily reflective of the California public education system.

- A secondary measure of education attainment in the state is the California Assessment of Student Performance and Progress (CAASPP).⁸ The 2024 CAASPP results showed that 52.95% of students did not meet or nearly met the state standard in English and 64.46% of students falling short for state standards in math.⁸ The CAASPP results show persistent achievement gaps between students who are economically disadvantaged, African American or Hispanic, and/or English learners, compared to their peers.⁹ There are concerns that standardized tests are biased and narrow classroom curriculums, yet they remain a staple assessment of academic outcomes.¹⁰ Additionally, the California School Dashboard measures chronic absenteeism, suspension rate, English learner progress, graduation rate, college/career, English language arts, and mathematics.¹¹

Student Loan Debt

- The percentage of college graduates with student loan debt reflects access to higher education and its financial burden. In California, 46% of graduating college students have loan debt.² Subsidized and unsubsidized federal loans account for the majority (64%) of student loan debt in California, though the rate of borrowing has declined from 2012 to 2020.⁶ Students who left college without graduating also face the burden of student loan debt, but this statistic is not captured in the data. Higher education costs, including (but not limited to) loan debt, may deter college attendance and exacerbate gaps by student groups, affecting long-term financial stability and mobility. California performs relatively well compared to other states in terms of in-state tuition costs. However, high cost of living is a significant factor contributing to the financial burden of higher education. We also considered other indicators relating to higher education quality such as persistence and completion rates.

DATA SNAPSHOT

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EDUCATION

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- Approved in 2023, [California Senate Bill 114](#) introduced Education Code Section 53008, which outlines new requirements for assessing students from kindergarten to grade two for reading difficulties. Intervention in early education helps provide a solid educational foundation for students, increasing engagement and morale while reducing behavioral problems.^{12,13}
- [California Senate Bill 153, Section 113](#) allows one-time funds totaling \$25 million for administering assessment screenings for reading difficulties.^{14,15}
- [California Assembly Bill 1454](#) advances evidence-based literacy instruction in the state's schools.^{16,17}
- The 2020 [California Assembly Bill 376](#) expands the rights of student loan borrowers by prohibiting loan service providers from providing inaccurate information or taking advantage of borrowers.^{18,19}

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Race and ethnicity are crucial to consider in the context of education in California. Black students are more likely to be suspended or expelled from schools, leading to greater interaction with law enforcement and perpetuating the school-to-prison pipeline.²⁰ Black and Pacific Islander students are also most likely to graduate college with student loan debt.²¹
- Native and Indigenous students face additional disparities, with the highest levels of absenteeism among racial and ethnic groups and high rates of students in the foster care system and/or with a disability.²² It is important to consider the painful history of boarding schools that functioned to assimilate Native and Indigenous students into the broader US culture.²³ There is mixed progress in overcoming disparities in education access, but further changes must be made in close collaboration with tribal communities.²⁴
- Students who are English language learners lag behind their peers in displaying grade-level proficiency and literacy rates.²⁵ English learners need access to high-quality language learning services and culturally affirming multilingual opportunities to improve outcomes.²⁶
- Students with disabilities face disproportionate issues in accessing education when compared to other students. This is due in part to a shortage in the number of special education teachers active in the state.²⁷

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ENERGY

According to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 7, everyone should have the right to affordable, reliable, and sustainable energy.³

Globally, access to electricity continues to increase, reaching 91% in 2021, yet 675 million people still remain without access.⁴ In the United States, energy access is widespread, but energy affordability is a persistent challenge, especially for low-income groups.⁵ California is no exception, with high energy costs that disproportionately impact low-income communities. Additionally, California is contending with more frequent extreme events, particularly wildfires, which impact energy reliability. The state has demonstrated a commitment to transition to renewable energy, but still faces significant challenges modernizing the grid while keeping energy affordable and reliable.⁶ Renewable energy data is included in the Climate Change category, so we focus on affordability and reliability data for this Energy category.

California's high energy costs and more frequent extreme events impact energy cost burden and energy reliability, both of which disproportionately affect low-income communities.

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ENERGY

SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

20%

Shortfall in affordable energy (energy burden)

7%

Shortfall in energy reliability

WHAT WE MEASURED

Energy Burden

- Energy burden, measured by energy costs relative to household income, is a common indicator to understand inequities within the energy sector.⁷ Most studies demarcate “severe energy burden” as households spending $\geq 10\%$ of income on energy. In California, almost 20% of total households have a severe energy burden, compared to 13% of total U.S. households.^{1, 8} Energy burden data is measured by home utility bills for electricity and fossil gas. This data excludes vehicle gas expenses, which represent a significant additional cost burden for California households.

Energy Reliability

- Energy reliability, measured by the frequency and duration of power outages, is another factor in understanding overall performance and disparities within an energy system. In California, in addition to outages caused by utility equipment failures, outages are also commonly caused when utilities turn off power to specific areas to reduce the risk of fires (known as Public Safety Power Shutoffs or PSPS).⁹
- There is no wide consensus on the best thresholds for energy reliability, so we relied on guidance from PSE Healthy Energy to choose a target of <6 hours of total outage time per year. The 6-hour outage boundary was calculated by doubling California’s average SAIDI (System Average Interruption Duration Index; with Major Events, including Public Safety Power Shutoffs) in 2022.² It is the minutes of non-momentary electric interruptions, per year, that the average customer experienced. The 6-hour outage threshold was then used to determine which California counties were past the threshold. The percentage of the state’s population living in those counties was used to calculate percent shortfall.² Approximately 7% of California’s population live in counties with well below average energy reliability.²
- Low-income households sometimes decide to shut off air conditioning to save on energy bills, and in some cases the utility will turn off power due to lapses in payment. These gaps in power can be considered poverty-induced brownouts or blackouts, and are not captured in reliability data.¹⁰

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- [California Alternate Rates for Energy \(CARE\)](#) and [Family Electric Rate Assistance Program \(FERA\)](#) provide discounts on energy bills for income-qualified households.^{11, 12} Households that qualify for CARE or FERA can also receive the [Energy Savings Assistance Program](#), which provides no-cost weatherization to increase home energy efficiency.¹³
- [The Low-Income Household Energy Assistance Program](#) is a federally funded program aimed at assisting low-income households in meeting their energy needs.¹⁴

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Across the U.S., Black, Latino, and Native American households, as well as families residing in low-income multifamily housing, experience disproportionately high energy burdens.⁹ These communities also tend to live in less energy-efficient housing stock, are underrepresented in energy efficiency programs,¹⁵ and lack the resources and infrastructure to install solar, battery storage, and efficient appliances, which can improve energy affordability and reliability.¹⁶
- Low-income households in California are also more likely to have their power shut off after a heatwave due to inability to pay.¹⁷ Additionally, vulnerable and historically marginalized communities are also disproportionately impacted by power outages.¹⁸ Relatedly, scholars are highlighting structural “thermal insecurity.”¹⁹

- As California continues to deploy renewable energy and modernize the grid, Community Benefit Agreements (CBAs) are becoming the gold standard to provide ownership and wealth-building opportunities, and empower local communities.²¹ CBAs aim to counteract extractive, tokenizing, or even colonial processes that can shroud new renewable energy development and negatively impact local low-income, marginalized, and Indigenous communities.^{22, 23}

Map: Energy net cost burden by income quintile in census tract across California (e.g. 1 = lowest income bracket).²⁰ Color scale breaks between red (highly burdened) and green (not highly burdened) at 8.5% of net income, with yellow indicating the ratio is exactly the threshold. Gray areas indicate negative net income after essential expenses. This graphic uses a more stringent threshold of 8.5% of income compared to the 10% target used for the household energy burden indicator in our report.

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FURTHER READING

[Preventing Wildfires with Power Outages](#)

[Incorporating Equity In Energy Resilience](#)

[California Public Utilities Commission, High Fire Threat District Map](#)

[The Spectrum of Community Engagement to Ownership](#)

[Community Benefits Tools And California Clean Energy Projects](#)

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EQUITY

Equity is about ensuring that all individuals, regardless of their identity, have access to the resources, opportunities, and support needed to thrive.

The United States was founded on systems of slavery and colonialism, which established a culture of exclusion rooted in systemic racism. This entrenched racial hierarchy not only oppressed people of color but also set a precedent for the marginalization of other groups within the nation's social and economic systems, such as women, immigrants, and those with disabilities.³

Just as the U.S. established systems of racial hierarchy and exclusion, California followed similar patterns of genocide, discrimination, and forced labor. Indigenous peoples faced state-sanctioned genocide,⁴ Chinese immigrants endured exclusion laws and violence,⁵ Japanese Americans were incarcerated during WWII,⁶ and Mexican and Filipino workers faced exploitation.⁷ These legacies of violence and discrimination have deeply influenced California's social and economic structure, reinforcing racial inequities that persist today.

Legacies of violence and discrimination have deeply influenced California's social and economic structure, reinforcing racial inequities that persist today.

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EQUITY

SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

40%

Shortfall in racial equity in economic vitality, readiness, and connectedness

13%

Shortfall in wages between men and women

WHAT WE MEASURED

Racial Equity Index

- Racial inequity often intersects with other forms of marginalization, compounding disadvantages for people of color.³ The Racial Equity Index “inclusion score” measures how California performs in terms of racial gaps across nine indicators (median wage, unemployment, poverty, educational attainment, disconnected youth, school poverty, air pollution, commute time, and rent burden) and considers seven racial/ethnic groups for which data is reported by the census.¹ The score is not a percentage, but rather a rating between 1-100. In 2022, California scored 60 out of 100. For more on the methodology, visit the [National Equity Atlas](#).¹

Figure: Racial Equity Index, Inclusion score by indicator: California: 2021

Gender Pay Gap

- The gender pay gap is crucial for equity because it reflects systemic discrimination that undervalues women’s work. Addressing it ensures fair compensation, promotes economic equality, and challenges gender-based power imbalances. For this assessment, we used U.S. Census data on the median wage between men and women by state.² In 2023, women in California earned only 87 cents for every dollar earned by a man, and women of color fared significantly worse.² For every dollar a white man in California earns, Black women earn 61 cents, Pacific Islander women 56 cents, Native American women 54 cents, and Latinas only 44 cents.⁸

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- [California Assembly Bill 3121](#) (2020) created a California Reparations Task Force dedicated to examining the legacy of slavery and its impact on African Americans, with the goal of providing recommendations for reparations.⁹ In 2023, they issued the [California Reparations Report](#) to the state legislature.¹⁰
- Legislation to address current inequities and historic harm against Native Californian communities includes: [California Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act \(AB 978, 2001\)](#); [California Indian Education Act \(AB 132, 2019\)](#); [Tribal Energy Sovereignty Resolution 2019](#).^{11,12,13}
- [The Equal Pay Act](#) (most recently amended in 2017) prohibits wage differences based on sex, race, and ethnicity for substantially similar work.¹⁴ [See resource](#) for employees and employers.¹⁵
- The [Gender Recognition Act](#) (2017) allows residents to legally change their gender marker on state-issued documents to “nonbinary.”¹⁶

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- California is home to many historically marginalized groups who face systemic barriers and inequities. Some individuals face compounding challenges due to intersecting identities across different marginalized or underserved groups.³ While race and gender are noteworthy, there are other lines of systemic discrimination and marginalization, including:

LGBTQ+

- California is widely recognized for promoting equity for all sexual orientations and gender identities. According to the Movement Advancement Project LGBTQ Policy Tally California Profile, the state performs high (45 points out of 49 possible, as of March 1, 2025) in terms of existing LGBTQ+ policies.¹⁷ This tally covers policies on relationship and parental recognition, nondiscrimination laws, healthcare, criminal justice, and more. Although policies play an essential role in influencing the experience of equality for LGBTQ+ people, they do not reflect the entire social climate in a state. Despite California’s legal protections, instances of discrimination persist across various sectors including in the workplace, educational institutions, and the healthcare system.¹⁸

Migrant workers

- Migrant workers are essential to California’s economy, particularly in agriculture, which generates almost \$60 billion annually and supplies a large share of the nation’s produce.¹⁹ Despite their vital contributions, these workers face harsh conditions, low wages, and limited protections. Many endure wage theft, poor housing, and lack access to healthcare.^{20,21} Undocumented workers are especially vulnerable, fearing retaliation if they report abuses.²² Exploitative labor recruitment practices also leave many in debt.²³ While policies like farmworker overtime laws aim to help, systemic inequities persist.²⁴

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FURTHER READING

[The Racial Equity Index](#)

[LGBTQ+ Policy Tally](#)

[Talking About Race](#)

[University of California Berkeley,
Center for Race and Gender](#)

[University of California Merced,
Native American & Indigenous
Communities Guide](#)

[History of Native California](#)

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FOOD

Globally, it is estimated that 2.3 billion people (28% of total population) are facing moderate to severe food insecurity, and 2.8 billion people are unable to afford a healthy diet.^{3, A}

In the United States, 12.2% of households are experiencing food insecurity, and poor nutrition is a concern for much of the country.^{1,4} In California, food insecurity is hovering just below the national average. Paralleling national trends, food insecurity in the state has been increasing since 2019, likely due to the lasting impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. Food intersects with numerous socio-ecological factors, which are increasingly integrated in transdisciplinary research on planetary health and human wellbeing.⁵ However, for this assessment, we keep a narrow focus on indicators related to food access and basic nutrition.

A. There are slight differences in the definition of “food security” between the USDA definition, which uses households as the unit of measurement, compared to global organizations, such as UNICEF and the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), which uses individuals as the unit.

In California, food insecurity is below the national average. Food insecurity in the state has been increasing since 2019, likely due to the lasting impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.¹

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FOOD

SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

11%

Shortfall in household food security

41%

Shortfall in adults who eat at least one serving of vegetables per day

WHAT WE MEASURED

Food Insecurity

- According to the United States Department of Agriculture's Economic Research Service (USDA ERS), food insecurity is defined as *households that are uncertain of having, or unable to acquire, at some time during the year, enough food to meet the needs of their members because they had insufficient money or other resources for food*. The ERS annually updates state food insecurity statistics by averaging the prevalence rates from the 3 most recent years. For this assessment, we use the most recent available data for California (2021-23), which shows that 11.4% of households are food insecure, of which 4.1% are very food insecure, according to self-reported information on food intake.^{1,6}

Vegetables per Day

- The California Department of Public Health (CDPH) dashboard tracks state and county-level data related to healthy diets and nutrition.² For this assessment, we chose to use *the percent of adults who eat ≥ 1 serving(s) of vegetables per day* as a proxy for healthy eating patterns in the state. According to the CDPH data from 2022, 59.2% of Californians eat at least one serving of vegetables per day.²
- The CDPH dashboard highlights that roughly half of California's population report that fruits and vegetables are sometimes unaffordable. The same dashboard contains data on obesity rates, food insecurity, food access, affordability, and racial/ethnic disparities.²

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- [The School Meals for All Program of 2022 \(Education Code 49501.5 and 49564.3\)](#) addresses food insecurity while promoting better health and academic outcomes by ensuring that every student has access to nutritious meals during the school day.⁷
- [California Senate Bill 907](#) in 2022 established the Local, Equitable Access to Food (LEAF) Program to expand the use of Electronic Benefit Transfer (EBT) systems at certified farmers' markets. This initiative increases availability of fresh, locally grown produce to low-income communities, improving food access and supporting local farmers.⁸

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FOOD

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

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- Racial and ethnic disparities in food insecurity have been a persistent trend across the United States for decades, with a clear gap between people of color and white population groups.⁹
- In California, according to 2022 CDPH data, African American, Latino, Pacific Islander, American Indian/Alaska Natives, and multiracial households experience higher rates of food insecurity than White and Asian ethnic groups.¹⁰
- Low-income families in California (<200% of the Federal Poverty Line) also experienced much higher rates of food insecurity: 41.5% in comparison to the state average of 11%.^{10, B}

FURTHER READING

[University of California San Francisco Seligman Research Lab](#) provides policy-oriented research on factors impacting the food environment and food affordability.

[The California Department of Public Health \(CDPH\)](#) provides a periodically updated resource on food security and nutrition access data in California.

B. There are slight differences in the survey and classifications of food insecurity between the USDA and California Department of Public Health, which relies on the California Health Interview Survey. However, these data are similar enough to provide a useful comparison.

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HEALTH

Public health in California reflects a mix of progress and persistent challenges.

While the state offers extensive healthcare resources, disparities in access remain, with structurally disadvantaged communities struggling to obtain adequate care.⁴ Both physical and mental health inequities are created through underlying social, economic, environmental factors which are systemic and therefore unjust.⁴ Chronic conditions like high blood pressure, affecting 28.4% of adults, and heart disease, the leading cause of death, continue to impact many residents.⁵ Mental health concerns, including anxiety and depression, contribute to rising hospitalizations and emergency visits, further straining healthcare systems.⁶

Additionally, environmental factors, such as wildfire smoke exposure, pose long-term health risks and have been linked to increased dementia rates.⁷ Pollution burdens and health disparities are especially stark between different racial/ethnic groups and income levels.¹³ Overall, it is alarming that from 2023 to 2025, average life expectancy in California has gone down from 81.0 to 79.4 years.¹

Between 2023 and 2025, the average life expectancy in California has gone down from 81.0 to 79.4 years¹

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HEALTH

SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

32%

 Shortfall based on population in counties below the average life expectancy in OECD countries

53%

 Shortfall in healthcare affordability, based on adults reducing healthcare use due to costs

WHAT WE MEASURED

Life Expectancy

- Life expectancy is a key health indicator because it reflects the overall well-being of a population by capturing the effects of healthcare access, disease prevalence, socioeconomic factors, and public health interventions.⁸ A higher life expectancy suggests better living conditions and healthcare systems, while a lower one may indicate health disparities, chronic disease burdens, or inadequate medical resources.^{8,A} The OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) is an international organization of 38 developed countries, and comparing local health indicators to its average provides a benchmark for assessing a country's healthcare performance relative to similar economies. While the OECD average life expectancy at birth in 2023 was 80.⁹ years,² during the same year life expectancy in 63% of California's counties, which contain 32% of its population, was below this benchmark.^{1,B}

Healthcare Affordability

- The percentage of adults who reduced their healthcare utilization due to costs serves as a critical indicator for the state's healthcare access and affordability.³ In the United States, high healthcare costs often lead individuals to forgo necessary medical care, resulting in worsened health outcomes and increased long-term expenses. This issue is particularly pronounced among uninsured and underinsured populations, who face significant financial barriers to accessing care.⁹ According to the California Health Care Foundation survey, 53% of adults in California report that they delayed, skipped, or reduced healthcare in the past year due to cost, and nearly half of those say this made their condition worse.³

- A. Some studies focus on healthy life expectancy (HALE), disability-adjusted life years (DALY) and similar measures that better account for quality of life.¹⁶ We decided to stay with overall life expectancy at birth for comparability with OECD data.
- B. Life expectancy data is available for California counties up until 2025, however we choose to keep the year consistent with the latest available OECD life expectancy data.^{1,2}

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

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- [Senate Bill 184 \(2022\)](#): Established the Office of Health Care Affordability (OHCA) within the Department of Health Care Access and Information. OHCA is responsible for monitoring and controlling healthcare spending, aiming to align spending growth with the state's economic growth rate.
- [Proposition 35, passed in 2024](#), permanently extends an existing tax on managed healthcare plans to fund Medi-Cal services, ensuring continued support for low-income Californians. The measure directs these funds exclusively toward healthcare services rather than replacing existing state spending.
- [Senate Bill 1016](#), the Latino and Indigenous Disparities Reduction Act, was signed into law in 2024. The legislation mandates that the California Department of Public Health collect and report detailed demographic data on Latino and Indigenous populations to better address health disparities.¹⁰

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

Health inequities in California impact life expectancy, access to care, and chronic disease rates, with disparities across race and geography.

- Black Californians have the lowest life expectancy at 74.6 years, compared to 85.7 years for Asian Californians, based on 2022 data.¹¹
- Native communities in California face significant health disparities, with a life expectancy of 71.8 years and suicide rates of 28.1 deaths per 100,000 people—the highest among all racial and ethnic groups. They are also 2.3 times more likely to die from diabetes than white individuals.¹²

- In 2021, 18% of Latino/x Californians lacked a usual source of care, and 15% delayed care, with 38% citing cost as the reason.¹³
- Rural northern California experiences higher rates of lung cancer, respiratory diseases, drug-induced liver diseases, and suicides due to elevated tobacco use, substance use, and mental health challenges, compared to California overall.¹⁴

Figure: Adults with chronic conditions, by race/ethnicity, California 2021.¹⁵ Source: California Health Care Foundation. (2024). Health Disparities by Race and Ethnicity in California Almanac, 2024 Edition. Downloadable Charts, Nr. 30. <https://www.chcf.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/DisparitiesAlmanacRaceEthnicity2024Charts.zip>

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HOUSING

Access to safe and affordable housing is widely recognized as a human right.⁴

It is the bedrock of stability, security, and overall well-being. Unfortunately, despite California’s incredible economic productivity as the 4th largest economy in the world, residents experience significant challenges trying to meet this most basic need.⁵

A combination of factors contribute to California’s housing crisis and shortage of affordable housing: wages relative to housing costs, low homeownership rates, high construction costs, permitting delays, zoning restrictions, NIMBYism, and others. This situation is forcing millions to spend an unreasonable portion of their income on housing costs, move out of California, or live without a home at all.

Overall, California falls short in providing affordable housing to residents and is home to the largest population of people experiencing homelessness in the United States.⁶

California falls short in providing affordable housing and is home to the largest homeless population in the U.S.⁶

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SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

36%

Shortfall in housing access based on homelessness rates

55%

Shortfall in housing affordability based on housing cost burden

WHAT WE MEASURED

Homelessness

- To secure federal funding for homelessness programs, California's regional Continuums of Care programs conduct a Point-in-Time (PIT) count at least every other year on a designated night in January. This count aims to estimate the number of people experiencing homelessness, both sheltered and unsheltered.⁷ In 2024, the count showed 187,084 unhoused people (0.47% of the population) across California. To measure the severity of the issue, the shortfall percentage is calculated using a scale where 0% represents the goal and 100% corresponds to the highest recorded homelessness rate within all OECD^A countries, which is 1.32% in Northern Ireland.² Since California's homelessness rate is 0.47%, the shortfall is calculated as $(0.47/1.32) \times 100 \approx 36\%$. This calculation depends on external comparisons, so alternative approaches might be explored in the future.

A. "OECD countries" refers to member nations of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

Housing Cost Burden

- The threshold for housing burden is when housing costs exceed 30% of household income. Staying below 30% for housing costs promotes financial security and offers a standardized measure of affordability, with some flexibility for local variations. It is a guideline, not a strict rule, but a valuable tool for understanding housing costs. Exceeding this threshold limits discretionary income for other essentials and savings, hindering financial security and investment potential.⁸ In California, 55% of renters have housing costs that exceed 30% of household income.³ The Housing Burden indicator used in this assessment focuses on rent costs instead of mortgage costs, as renting is more common among lower-income households and reflects more immediate changes in housing affordability.⁹ Although mortgage costs vary due to interest rates, loan terms, and home equity, mortgages in California are quite high, representing a significant barrier to homeownership. In California, 38% of mortgaged homeowners spend more than 30% of their income on housing costs, compared to 20% nationwide.³

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Reviewed by:

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- Since 2019, the state has invested over \$27 billion to support local governments in providing services and housing to help prevent and end homelessness, including \$3.3 billion for Homekey,¹⁰ \$1 billion in Encampment Resolution Funding,¹¹ and \$4.85 billion in Homelessness Housing Assistance Program funds.¹²
- In 2023, [SB 423](#) was passed to streamline the permitting process for building multifamily housing developments. This extends provisions from SB 35 (Wiener, 2017), which were effective in expanding affordable housing.¹³
- California voters passed [Proposition 1](#) in March of 2024, which included \$6.38 billion in funding to develop and expand behavioral health treatment, residential care settings, and supportive housing. Of this, \$1.05 billion funds supportive housing for homeless veterans with mental health or substance use disorders, and \$922 million supports housing for those experiencing or at risk of homelessness with behavioral health needs.¹⁴
- In 2024, California allocated over \$91 million to support affordable housing and homelessness interventions for Native American communities. This includes \$71 million for permanent rental units through the Tribal Homekey program and \$20 million for culturally responsive homelessness prevention via the Tribal HHAP program.¹⁵

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- California's homeless crisis disproportionately impacts some groups more than others. Black Californians in particular, experience homelessness at disproportionately high rates. Despite making up about 6% of the state's population, Black Californians accounted for over 20% of the total homeless population.¹
- Black and Latino homeownership are both far below average homeownership rates in California, which are well below national homeownership rates. This illustrates how certain communities are excluded from the generational wealth-building opportunities associated with homeownership.¹⁶
- This disparity stems from systemic issues like historical racism and discrimination in housing, employment, and healthcare. These barriers create a cycle of disadvantage that makes it harder for people of color to purchase a home, leaving them more vulnerable to homelessness.¹⁶
- Discrimination, violence and incarceration all compound the likelihood of experiencing a mental health or substance use issue and ultimately increase risk of homelessness for individuals.¹⁷
- Furthermore, incarceration also limits the housing options available to the person - due to discrimination from landlords, laws about who can live in Section 8 housing, and individual barriers, like lack of employment or savings.¹⁸

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INCOME & WORK

California faces significant challenges with poverty, driven largely by its high cost of living, especially housing.

When considering metrics that account for living costs, the state consistently ranks among those with the highest poverty levels in the U.S. Poverty rates have risen further with the expiration of pandemic-era relief policies, which had previously provided crucial support to many low-income households.³ Despite having one of the largest economies in the world, California also has some of the starkest disparities in income and wealth, with a growing divide between affluent communities and those struggling to meet basic needs.⁴

California has some of the starkest disparities in income and wealth.⁴

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INCOME & WORK

SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

15%

Shortfall based on people experiencing poverty

9%

Shortfall in employment, based on un- and underemployment rate

WHAT WE MEASURED

Poverty

- The Supplemental Poverty Measure (SPM) from the United States Census Bureau offers a broader evaluation of poverty in the United States by incorporating non-cash benefits, tax credits, and necessary expenses, thereby reflecting the actual economic conditions faced by families more accurately than the official poverty measure, which relies solely on cash income and fixed thresholds.¹
- The Census Bureau recommends a 3-year average of SPM to increase statistical reliability. California's 3-year average SPM (2021, 2022, 2023) is 15.4%, one of the highest in the U.S.¹
- In 2023, California's Supplemental Poverty Measure rose to 18.9%, significantly higher than the national SPM of 12.9%.³ This means that approximately 7.3 million Californians live in poverty, highlighting the state's persistent challenges with economic disparity and high living costs.³

Unemployment (U-6)

- The U-6 rate is California's broadest measure of labor underutilization. It includes the unemployed, those employed part-time for economic reasons (involuntary part time), and marginally attached workers. According to the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, in 2023, California had a U-6 rate of 9.3%.² This figure is notably higher than the national U-6 rate of 6.9%.²

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Berkeley

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- While many of California's social safety net programs, such as [CalWORKs](#),⁵ [Medi-Cal](#),⁶ and [CalFresh](#),⁷ are based on federal initiatives, the state often expands and tailors them through policies to meet the needs of its large and diverse population.
- California stands out with its comprehensive employment services alongside cash assistance through CalWORKs, its expansive Medi-Cal program that includes coverage for undocumented individuals in some cases, and its proactive approach to CalFresh with higher eligibility thresholds and streamlined applications.
- The state's unique affordable housing initiatives, like the [Homekey project](#),⁸ aim to address the housing crisis, while its [subsidized childcare](#) programs provide robust support for working parents.⁹
- In addition, California's minimum wage is one of the highest in the United States, significantly surpassing the federal minimum wage and exceeding the minimum wage in many other states.¹⁰
- Furthermore, tax credits play a crucial role in the social safety net system in the U.S. The [California Earned Income Tax Credit](#) (CalEITC) is a refundable tax credit designed to provide financial relief to low-income working individuals and families in California.¹¹ It can either reduce the amount of taxes owed or result in a refund if the credit exceeds the taxes due.

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- The economic disparity is particularly pronounced among communities of color, with poverty rates for Black and Latinx residents at 22.3% and 25%, respectively.¹
- As of early 2024, the U-6 rate for Black individuals was notably higher at 8.2%, compared to 5.8% for Hispanic individuals and 4.8% for White individuals.^{12, 13}
- Gender-based injustice is also evident in gender pay gaps, which is included in the [Equity section](#) of this report.

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PEACE & JUSTICE

According to Sustainable Development Goal 16, people everywhere should live free of the fear of violence and feel safe regardless of their ethnicity, faith, or sexual orientation.⁴

The United States has far more violent crimes (especially homicides) compared to other high-income countries, largely due to the prevalence of gun violence.⁵ Despite having dropped significantly over the last 30 years, California's violent crime rate remains well above the United States' national average.⁶ California also has significant room for improvement with respect to fair policing and police violence. The high-profile police killing of Oscar Grant in 2009 in Oakland brought more public and policy attention to police violence and to the stark racial disparities in policing.^{7,8} However, despite policing reforms, between 2013 and 2023 California had more police killings per arrest than 73% of U.S. states.^{3,9} This report focuses on violent crimes and policing, but we acknowledge that these indicators merely scratch the surface of this multifaceted topic.

In addition to these local indicators, we highlight the alignment of military contracts and lobbying activity in California, exposing profit incentives for war, militarization, and political violence abroad.

Despite having dropped significantly over the last 30 years, California's violent crime rate remains well above the United States' national average.⁶

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SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

100%

Shortfall based on the percent of people living in counties with a violent crime rate above 200 per 100,000 people

65%

Shortfall based on the Police Scorecard (averaged score for police funding, accountability, violence and approach to law enforcement)

WHAT WE MEASURED

Violent Crime

- The United States Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) publishes annual data on violent crimes reported to law enforcement in each state.² By definition this data misses violent crimes that were not reported. For geographic comparison within the United States, data is commonly normalized as a violent crime rate based on the number of violent incidents per 100,000 residents. Violent crime rates rose in California after the pandemic and still remain above pre-pandemic levels.¹⁰ However, crime trends fluctuate geographically, with some cities experiencing higher rates of violent offenses such as homicides, aggravated assaults, and robberies, while others have seen reductions.⁹ Overall, California's violent crime rate was 36% above the U.S. national average (see figure).⁴ To account for regional variability, we calculated the shortfall by measuring the percentage of California residents living in counties with a violent crime rate above the best-performing states, which tend to be below 200 violent crimes per 100,000

people.² Based on 2023 data from the California Department of Justice, only one of California's 58 counties (Sierra County) was below this threshold, so 99.9% of residents live in counties that don't meet this high-bar for public safety. [See supplemental calculations.](#)

Police Scorecard

- This indicator on police violence and fair policing practices helps assess whether all communities are treated fairly and equally, particularly marginalized groups. The Police Scorecard Project conducts a standardized evaluation for every state in the U.S based on levels of police violence, accountability, racial bias and other policing outcomes.³ It provides an averaged score in four specific areas: police funding, accountability, violence and approach to law enforcement.³ Across these four areas, California received an average score of 35%, which translates to a 65% social shortfall.³
- Additionally, we considered an indicator to assess California's role in militarization and undermining peace and justice globally. In 2023, California received \$60.5 billion dollars from the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) budget, primarily in the form of defense-related contracts.¹¹ Three of the top five largest private recipients of these DoD contracts, Lockheed Martin, Raytheon/RTX, and Northrop Grumman, maintain significant operations in California.¹¹ According to OpenSecrets, each of these three companies also spent more money on lobbying than any other defense company, collectively spending over \$10 million in the 2023-2024 election cycle.¹² The alignment between contract money and political influence underscores profit incentives for war and militarization within California's economic and political ecosystem. Future research could work to establish a reasonable benchmark with this set of information.

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FURTHER READING

[Crime Trends](#), Public Policy Institute of California, 2025

[Reimagining community safety](#), Catalyst California, 2023

[The Jakarta Method \(2020\)](#) by Vincent Bevins, recounts the United States' role in political violence abroad.

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- The [Racial and Identity Profiling Act \(RIPA\)](#) of 2015 (AB 953) expanded the definition of racial profiling and mandated that all law enforcement agencies collect and report detailed data on stops, including the perceived race or ethnicity of individuals stopped.¹³
- Building on RIPA, the [California Racial Justice Act of 2020 \(AB 2542\)](#) prohibits the state from seeking or obtaining criminal convictions or imposing sentences based on race, ethnicity, or national origin. This legislation allows individuals to challenge their cases if there is evidence of racial bias or disparities in charges, convictions, or sentencing.¹⁴
- [California Senate Bill 1421 of 2019](#) aims to improve police transparency and accountability by making records of police misconduct and use of force incidents publicly accessible.¹⁵

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

Disparities in violent crime and unfair policing in California are deeply rooted in factors of racial, social, and economic inequality.

- The 2024 Racial and Identity Profiling Advisory (RIPA) Board report revealed significant disparities in policing.¹⁶ Black Californians were stopped 131% more frequently than their population proportion, and Native Americans faced the highest search rates at 22.4%, compared to 12.4% for White individuals. Despite these higher search rates, officers found contraband less frequently on people of color than on White individuals. Black students in schools with police presence were stopped and handcuffed at higher rates than other racial groups. LGBTQ+ and people with mental health disabilities are overrepresented in stand-alone resisting arrest charges, which suggests identity profiling.¹⁷
- Low-income communities of color are more likely to be incarcerated and victimized by violent crimes.^{18,19}

Violent crime in California

Crime reported to police per 100,000 residents

Figure: FBI Uniform Crime Reporting Program SRS state estimates.⁶

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POLITICAL VOICE

Political voice is the ability of people to express their views, engage in political processes, and influence government actions.

In the 2024 U.S. presidential election, voter turnout remained high, with over 153 million votes cast nationwide, nearing 2020 levels. In California, turnout declined, with approximately 16 million voters participating—1.7 million fewer than in 2020—despite an increase in both registered and eligible voters.^{3,4}

Voter turnout in California varies significantly between election types, with higher participation in presidential elections and lower engagement in midterm and local races. For instance, in the 2020 presidential election, 81% of registered California voters cast ballots, whereas the 2022 midterm election saw a turnout of only 51%; the presidential election in 2024 then had a 71% turnout of registered voters.^{1,5}

Policies like universal mail-in voting have improved access, but factors such as economic concerns, political disillusionment, and demographic disparities continue to influence participation.⁶

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POLITICAL VOICE

SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

40%

Shortfall in eligible voter turnout

16%

Shortfall in eligible voters who are registered

WHAT WE MEASURED

Voter Turnout

- Eligible voter turnout refers to the percentage of the voting-eligible population that participates in an election, reflecting civic engagement and access to the electoral process.
- Historical voter participation data shows that in the November 2024 presidential election, about 60% of eligible voters in California cast their ballot, compared to over 70% in 2020. In absolute terms, over 10.7 million eligible California voters did not vote in 2024.¹

Registered Voters

- The percentage of eligible voters who are not registered to vote represents the share of the voting-eligible population that has not completed the registration process required to cast a ballot. A lower percentage indicates a higher level of voter registration, while a higher percentage suggests that many eligible individuals are not taking part in the electoral process.
- Historical voter registration data shows that before the November 2024 presidential election, about 84% of eligible voters in California were registered, compared to almost 88% in 2020. In absolute terms, over 4.3 million eligible California voters did not register to vote in 2024.²

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- Automatic Voter Registration (AVR):** Since 1993, the National Voter Registration Act, often known as the Motor Voter law, has helped millions of people register to vote or update their voter information during a driver license or ID card transaction at the California Department of Motor Vehicles (DMV). Recent program changes have eligible individuals automatically registered to vote during DMV transactions unless they opt out. This initiative aims to increase voter participation by streamlining the registration process.
- Voter's Choice Act (VCA):** Enacted through Senate Bill 450 in 2016, the VCA modernizes elections by mailing every registered voter a ballot, expanding in-person early voting, and allowing voters to cast ballots at any vote center within their county. This model provides greater flexibility and convenience, encouraging higher voter turnout.

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

Californians who are most likely to vote continue to be disproportionately white, affluent, college-educated, and homeowners.⁷

- White adults account for 50% of likely voters but only 38% of the state's population.⁸
- Latino adults make up 26% of likely voters while representing 36% of the population.⁸
- Asian American residents comprise 15% of likely voters and 16% of the population.⁸
- Black residents represent 5% of both likely voters and the overall population.⁸

Most of the 4.7 million eligible but unregistered voters in the state are Black, Latino or Asian American and Pacific Islander. This represents the largest unregistered state electorate in the country, and surpasses the population of 24 states.⁷ California must continue to improve its voter registration system and support community-based organizations that educate and engage voters.

California's likely voters differ from its population

Figure: Percent likely voters vs. percent California population. Source: Public Policy Institute of California, from seven PPIC Statewide Surveys from September 2023 to July 2024, and US Census Bureau 2018–2022 American Community Survey.⁸

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SOCIAL COHESION

Social cohesion refers to the strength of relationships and the sense of solidarity among members of a community.

It encompasses shared values, trust, and a sense of belonging, enabling individuals to feel part of a common enterprise and to face shared challenges together.²

In California, income inequality has significantly increased over recent decades, positioning the state among those with the widest income disparities in the nation. Between 1980 and 2022, there has been a 68% income increase for the highest earners and a modest 10% rise for the lowest earners in California. As of 2023, only two other states exhibited wider income gaps.⁴

Research indicates that higher income inequality correlates with lower levels of happiness and well-being, as individuals may engage in unfavorable social comparisons, decreasing trust and social cohesion.⁵ Studies show that social participation and perceived neighborhood cohesion positively impact individual happiness and well-being, enhancing feelings of safety, support, and belonging.^{6,7}

In California, income inequality has significantly increased over recent decades, positioning the state among those with the widest income disparities in the nation.⁴

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SHORTFALL

SOCIAL COHESION

PERFORMANCE

100%

Shortfall in counties with low income inequality (Gini Index below 0.30)

26%

Shortfall in people reporting happiness

WHAT WE MEASURED

Gini Index

- The Gini Index (or Gini coefficient) measures income or wealth inequality within a population. It ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 represents perfect equality (everyone has the same income) and 1 represents maximum inequality (one person has all the income, and everyone else has none). A higher Gini Index indicates greater income inequality, while a lower Gini Index suggests a more equal distribution of income. It is commonly used to assess economic disparities within countries, states, or regions. In 2023, not a single one of the 58 counties in CA had a Gini Index below 0.30, the target threshold suggested by Fanning et al.² In all of them, income inequality was higher than 0.40, with a statewide average of 0.49.¹

Figure: Chart shows percent change in CA family income before taxes, adjusted for inflation in 2023 dollars. Income is normalized to reflect the equivalent of a family of four. Graphic from Public Policy Institute of California.⁵

Report Not Happy

- Since 1998, the Public Policy Institute of California has conducted a statewide survey about a range of issues important to Californians, including reported happiness. The survey asks "Taken all together, how would you say things are these days? Would you say you are:" with answer choices of "pretty happy", "very happy" and "not too happy" The latest survey data from 2023 reports 26% of Californians report being "not too happy."²

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- The California Earned Income Tax Credit (CalEITC) was established through [Senate Bill 80](#) in 2015. This legislation introduced a supplemental cash-back credit aimed at assisting low-income working families. The program has since undergone several expansions and modifications to increase its reach and effectiveness. In 2017, [Senate Bill 106](#) expanded CalEITC by including self-employment income and adjusting the credit amounts. In 2020, Governor Gavin Newsom further expanded CalEITC, increasing the investment to over \$1 billion and introducing the Young Child Tax Credit (YCTC) to provide additional support to families with children under six.⁸
- The Reparations Task Force ([Assembly Bill 3121, 2020](#)) was established to study and develop proposals for compensating African Americans for historical injustices, with ongoing legislative efforts to implement recommendations.

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- California's income inequality is deeply tied to racial and geographic disparities. Black and Latino workers earn significantly less than white workers, with Black women facing some of the widest wage gaps.⁹ Latino families in affluent areas like Marin County are more likely to struggle financially compared to white families.¹⁰
- Geographically, income inequality varies widely, with lower-income communities concentrated in the Central Valley and Inland Empire facing higher unemployment and fewer economic opportunities.⁴
- Immigrants — especially undocumented workers — are disproportionately represented in low-wage industries, often facing barriers to upward mobility, labor protections, and access to public benefits, which exacerbates income inequality across the state.¹¹

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Access to clean drinking water and sanitation is a basic human need for health and well-being, according to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 6.

Globally, billions of people currently lack access to safe drinking water, sanitation, and hygiene, and we are not on track to address this global shortfall by 2030.³ Compared to global performance averages, California has relatively small problems with clean water, sanitation, and hygiene as a percentage of population, nevertheless data indicate that over a million residents in California lack access to either clean water or basic sanitation or both.

Over a million residents in California lack access to clean water, basic sanitation, or both.

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WATER & SANITATION

SHORTFALL

PERFORMANCE

2.2%

Shortfall in access to water from systems that meet drinking water quality standards

0.5%

Shortfall shortfall in basic access to sanitation

WHAT WE MEASURED

Water Quality

- Water quality performance is measured by the percentage of the California population who receive drinking water from systems that do not meet state and federal water quality standards, which include maximum contamination violations, E. coli violations, treatment violations, and monitoring and reporting violations.⁴ See full criteria in the CA Water Board [2024 Needs Assessment](#).⁴ Data on water quality violations is updated live on the SAFER website. As of May 2025, the [SAFER database](#) indicated 405 failing water systems, representing 883,169 people or 2.2% of California's total population.¹
- Regulatory water quality data does not include private wells, which are more likely to be unsafe, so the estimated number of people with unsafe drinking water in California is likely an undercount.⁵

Sanitation Access

- Sanitation data is lacking at the state level, so we use a study which estimates the lack of sanitation access in urban areas of the United States including California.² The study, which accounts for lack of sanitation due to homelessness and substandard housing, estimates that 214,930 urban residents in California lack basic sanitation.² California comprises 12% of the total US population, yet almost a quarter (23%) of total urban residents without basic sanitation are in California.²
- Sanitation data is currently only available for urban populations, as a result the data we present is known to be an underestimate.

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- In 2019, California passed [Senate Bill 200 \(SB 200\)](#), which enabled the State Water Resources Control Board (State Water Board) to create the Safe and Affordable Funding for Equity and Resilience Drinking Water (SAFER) program, to help high-risk water systems provide safe drinking water.⁶
- State Water Board [Resolution No. 2022-0019](#) and [2016-0010](#) recognize Californians' equal and human right to sanitation.^{7, 8} As a result, the state is undertaking a comprehensive [Wastewater Needs Assessment](#), which may provide more accurate California-specific sanitation data for future assessments.⁹

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FURTHER READING

[Water and Sanitation in Urban America, 2017–2019](#)

[State Water Resources Board SAFER Dashboard](#)

[Human Rights to Water Solutions Lab](#)

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Disadvantaged communities and communities of color are disproportionately impacted by unsafe water quality: 56% of failing public water systems serve disadvantaged communities, and 67% serve majority communities of color.⁴
- In the Central Valley, particularly in Southern San Joaquin Valley, groundwater pumping for agriculture has left shallower wells for drinking water dry or contaminated, primarily impacting low-income Latino populations.¹⁰
- Given sanitation data comes from California's homelessness and substandard housing statistics, the racial disparities in homelessness described in the [Housing section](#), particularly among Black residents, translate directly to a disproportionate lack of access to basic sanitation amongst the Black population.¹¹

Map: California water systems that are “Failing,” “At-Risk,” and “Potentially At-Risk” monitored by CA Water Board’s [SAFER website](#).¹ Shortfall calculations only accounted for people that rely on “Failing” systems.

ECOLOGICAL CEILING

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AIR POLLUTION

Air pollution is the second leading risk factor for death globally.

In 2021, air pollution (mostly particulate matter of diameters 2.5 micrometers and smaller, i.e. PM2.5) contributed to 8.1 million deaths around the world.³ Particulate matter (PM) and ozone (O3), which are both U.S. EPA criteria air pollutants, pose the greatest health risks, which is why we decided to focus on these pollutants as air pollution indicators.^{4,5} Sources of PM2.5 include vehicle exhaust, agriculture and livestock, construction, and industrial processes.⁶ In California in recent years, smoke from wildfires has caused spikes in PM2.5 pollution.⁷ Ground-level ozone is formed when nitrogen oxides (NOx) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are exposed to sunlight. NOx and VOCs similarly come from vehicles, power plants, refineries, and other sources.⁸

In California, wildfire smoke has caused spikes in particulate matter pollution.⁷

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OVERSHOOT

A. To calculate overshoot, we opted to use the percent of non-compliant air basins rather than the percent of the population living in these air basins because this indicator falls under the ecological rather than social dimension.

AIR POLLUTION

PERFORMANCE

60%

Overshoot in O₃ pollution:

60%

Overshoot in particulate matter

WHAT WE MEASURED

Ozone Pollution

- CARB has a designated ozone pollution standard of 0.07 parts per million (ppm) in an 8 hour period. The California standard is consistent with the national standard, based on more prevalent harmful health effects when ozone is above these designated levels.¹⁶ If the average of three years of fourth-highest daily maximum 8-hour averages is above 0.07ppm, the air basin is in violation of the ozone standard.¹⁰ Again using 2023 data from CARB's air pollution statistics tool, we found 9 of 15 (60%) air basins violate the state and national ozone standard.²

Particulate Matter

- The California Air Resource Board (CARB) has a current standard of 12 micrograms(g)/m³ for the annual averages for PM^{2.5} pollution (fine particulate matter).⁹ For this assessment, we used the more stringent national standard of 9g/m³, measured using an

Figure: [California EnviroScreen map of PM2.5 pollution by percentile](#), showing the highest-levels of particulate pollution are in the Southern Central Valley and the South Coast region around Los Angeles.¹⁵

average of 3-years of annual averages.¹⁰ This national standard was updated in 2024 based on scientific and equity-related considerations regarding margins of safety, and will likely be adopted at the state level soon.¹¹ Across the state, PM^{2.5} pollution has been reduced over the last 20 years.¹² However, based on 2023 data from CARB's air pollution statistics tool, we found that 9 of 15 air basins (60%) are in violation of the national standard.¹ In 2024, CARB produced a report with consistent but more precise findings, designating 9 non-attainment areas based on the national standard.¹³ Two basins well above the PM^{2.5} threshold were the San Joaquin Valley Air Basin (16.2 g/m³) and South Coast Air Basin (13.1 g/m³). The South Coast Air Basin alone is home to 17 million people or 44% of California's population.^{14, A}

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FURTHER READING

[The California Air Resources Board \(CARB\) iADAM tool](#) and [other maps and tools](#)
[CalEnviroScreen](#)

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- The Mulford-Carrell Air Resources Act of 1967 created the California State Air Resources Board (CARB). Since its creation, CARB has set state standards and monitored air quality.¹⁷
- With Assembly Bill 617 of 2017, CARB established the Community Air Protection Program to improve local air quality measurements and reduce exposure in the communities most affected by air pollution.¹⁸
- Advanced Clean Cars (ACC) & 2035 Gas Car Ban of 2022 is estimated to reduce over 4,000 tons of fine particulate matter (PM^{2.5}) and other harmful air pollution such as greenhouse gases from 2026 to 2040.¹⁹
- AB 32 Global Warming Solutions Act of 2006 (also mentioned in the [Climate Change](#) section), is an important piece of legislation setting greenhouse gas emissions reduction targets, often linked with local air quality improvement efforts.²⁰

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Redlining from the 20th century continues to impact Black, Hispanic, and low-income populations today. Formerly redlined neighborhoods have higher pollution burdens, less vegetation, and elevated temperatures, compared to city averages.²¹
- Studies consistently show a higher air pollution burden for low-income and people of color communities.²² According to a 2021 CalEnviroScreen Analysis of Race/Ethnicity, people of color, especially Latino and Black people, disproportionately reside in areas with high pollution burden in California.²³
- A comprehensive 2024 study conducted by UC Berkeley public health researchers found that minority populations were more likely to be exposed to elevated concentrations of PM_{2.5} and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), however pollution burden seems to be improving over time.²⁴ Unfortunately, the Indigenous or Native American demographic group was not disaggregated in these studies.

10% least impacted neighborhoods | 10% most impacted neighborhoods

Figure: Racial disparities in pollution burdens and vulnerabilities by census tract (CalEnviroScreen 4.0)²³

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BIODIVERSITY LOSS

Biodiversity refers to the variety of life forms that make up ecosystems. Biodiversity supports core Earth systems processes that humans depend on to survive.⁵

Today, species are going extinct faster than at any time since the dinosaurs. We are in the midst of a mass extinction event for the 6th time in the history of life on Earth.⁶

Changes in land-use, invasive species/disease, climate change, and pollution are the main threats to biodiversity.⁷ Over 90% of biodiversity loss is caused by the use and processing of natural resources.⁸ Humans directly impact 75% of ice-free land, mainly with agriculture, resource extraction, built-up land, and recreation.⁹

Today, species are going extinct faster than at any time since the dinosaurs.⁶

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OVERSHOOT

BIODIVERSITY LOSS

PERFORMANCE

59%

Overshoot in unprotected area

947%

Overshoot in animal and plant species at risk

WHAT WE MEASURED

Protected Area

- Protected areas leave a space for non-human life to flourish, while providing outdoor recreation which can also improve human well-being. Following the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework released in 2022, California adopted a target of 30% protected area by 2030. The United Nations and other scientific bodies advocate for a 2050 target of 50% protected area.^{10,11,12}
- Currently, about 25% of California's land and 16% of its sea area are protected.¹ Compared to the desired 50%, this means a 50% and 68% overshoot of unprotected land and sea, respectively.²

At-Risk Species

- Background rates of extinction are assumed to be somewhere between 0.1 and 1 species extinction per 10,000 species per 100 years (1 E/MSY). Today, extinction rates are between 10 and 100 times this rate. NatureServe⁷ estimates the number of plant and animal species that are imperiled or vulnerable in each state, while Pimm et al.⁴ estimate the percent of endangered species in preindustrial times.
- Currently, about 30% of California's animal species and 30% of its plant species are at risk of extinction.³ Compared to a baseline extinction rate of 3%, this means a 1000% and 890% overshoot, respectively.

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- 2030 California Target ([Executive Order N-82-20](#)): Minimum 30% of all land and sea areas are protected.
- 2050 World Target ([IUCN Motion 101](#)): Minimum 50% of all land and sea areas are protected.^{7,13}
- Between 2020 and 2024, protected land and water areas have increased from 24.0% to 25.2% and from 16.0% to 16.2% respectively.^{1,15}

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JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

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- Indigenous communities safeguard most of the world's remaining biodiversity.¹⁶ Meanwhile they are squeezed onto smaller and smaller tracts of land, forced out mainly by agriculture and resource extraction.

- Protected lands must be community conservation areas that support humans and nature thriving together, not be an iteration of imperial displacement.¹⁷

Map: The dark red areas of this map show the parts of the U.S. where biodiversity on land is most at risk.¹³ Notably, California has the highest concentration of species at risk.¹⁴

Airbus,USGS,NGA,NASA,CGIAR,NCEAS,NLS,OS,NMA,Geodatastyrelsen,GSA,GSI and the GIS User

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CHEMICAL POLLUTION

Chemical pollutants pose a significant threat to human health and ecosystem function.

In humans, chemicals can cause cancer, reproductive harm, and neurodevelopmental effects. Ecologically they can impact pollinators, contribute to dead zones, compromise coral reefs, and more.³ Globally, the planetary boundary for the release of novel entities—new anthropogenic introductions, including known and unknown chemical and plastic pollution—into the Earth system is hard to quantify due to lack of data in a fast-evolving space, but it is believed to be transgressed.^{4,13} Chemical pollution released into the air, land, or water comes from the production and use of consumer and commercial products, manufacturing processes, and waste disposal.³

At the global scale, it is difficult to identify quantifiable indicators for California that address the full scope of chemical pollution and its impacts. For example, an unknown amount of chemical pollution occurs through accidental or illegal disposal in the state. We highlight two sources of data that provide a snapshot of chemical pollution in California.

Globally, the planetary boundary for the release of novel entities is hard to quantify, but is believed to be transgressed.^{4,13}

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OVERSHOOT

- A. Depending on where we set the threshold and how we do the calculations, the percent overshoot could be much higher and was in a previous version. (e.g. if threshold was set at 5% and calculated using percent difference, paradoxically the overshoot would increase to 171% for toxic pesticides and 89% for toxic chemicals).
- B. We do not count oil-based pesticides towards overall toxic pesticide quantity because DPR's sustainable pest management (SPM) guidelines and the USDA organic rules both allow the use of oils, and the category includes natural oils in addition to petroleum-based oils.^{7,8} However, oils are not harmless to use and should be minimally applied in accordance with those SPM and organic guidelines. If oils are included in toxic amounts, the percentage rises to 84% of pesticides. [Supplemental calculation.](#)

CHEMICAL POLLUTION

PERFORMANCE^A

65%

Overshoot in toxic pesticides applied per year

13%

Overshoot in toxic chemicals released per year

WHAT WE MEASURED

Toxic Pesticides Applied

- California has the largest agriculture industry in the country, producing almost a third of the country's vegetables, fruits, and nuts.⁵ Agricultural production and household plant and pest management in CA involves significant use of pesticides and is regulated by the California Department of Pesticide Regulation (DPR). Certain pesticides are known to DPR to be toxic to humans and other organisms and are categorized as carcinogens, cholinesterase inhibitors, fumigants, groundwater contaminants, reproductive toxicants, and toxic air contaminants.¹ Additionally, the inert ingredients in many pesticides pose an unknown health and environmental risk due to the lack of available information on their application and effects.⁶

The remaining pesticides in use are biopesticides and oils which pose less risk to human and environmental health.^B Out of the total 181 million pounds of pesticides applied in 2022, 65% by weight are from the categories of pesticides considered most toxic.¹ Pesticides have been detected by DPR in groundwater wells, surface waters, and in ambient air, where they pose varying health risks.^{9,10,11} To prevent degradation of human and environmental health due to pesticides, the use of these most toxic pesticides should be minimized, with a goal of 0%.

Toxic Chemicals Released

- The US EPA tracks the management of a subset of toxic chemicals known to cause significant health and environmental effects through the Toxic Releases Inventory (TRI).¹² Industrial facilities in California report the quantities released of a specific list of chemicals and describe how the waste is managed. Of the 287 million pounds of TRI-listed toxic chemical waste produced in California in 2023, 13% was released into the air or water, placed in some type of land disposal, or transferred off-site for disposal or release, where it may impact humans and ecosystems.²

The threshold for toxic chemical releases is set at 0% to account for uncertainty in sustainability thresholds. Also, reporting under the TRI captures only a small subset of industrial chemicals in California and omits significant chemical releases from consumer and commercial products used in the state. We do recognize that releases under TRI include what is allowable under regulations in addition to accidental releases reported, but we conclude that California has to reduce chemical pollution to limit human and environmental impacts.

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Additional indicators considered

- Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential (FEP) estimates the consumption-based damage caused by toxic chemicals on freshwater ecosystems. The US EPA's environmentally-extended input-output model (USEEIO) aggregates California's FEP emissions of heavy metals, pesticides, and industrial chemicals into a unit called Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (CTUe), amounting to ~330 CTUe/person/year.¹³
- Waste sent to landfill and overseas reflects the potential to introduce novel materials into the earth ecosystem that can cause harm, in accordance with the planetary boundary established by Persson et al.¹⁴ CalRecycle actively measures the amount of waste sent to landfill, overseas, recycled, or reused within California. The state set a goal of achieving a recycling rate of 75% by 2020, which caps the amount of waste sent to landfill at 25%. The current overall recycling rate in 2022 was 41%, including 15% of recycling sent overseas.¹⁵

Figure: US EPA Toxic Releases Inventory Facilities in California, from [CalEnviroScreen 4.0](#).¹⁷

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- The [Pesticide Contamination Prevention Act of 1985](#) (PCPA) established requirements for identifying and regulating potential groundwater contaminants and their fate in the environment.
- The [California Green Chemistry Law of 2008](#) established the nation's first of its kind Safer Consumer Products (SCP) program to reduce the use of hazardous chemicals in consumer products and encourage safe alternatives.
- The [US Emergency Planning and Community Right-to-Know Act of 1986](#) (EPCRA) established the EPA TRI program to provide the public with information about chemical releases. It has since been updated to include new chemicals and industry sectors.
- The [California Safe Drinking Water and Toxic Enforcement Act of 1986](#) (known as Prop 65) requires businesses to warn the public about exposure to a list of over 900 chemicals that cause cancer, birth defects, or other reproductive harm. It also prohibits businesses from releasing listed chemicals into sources of drinking water.

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- The physical location of waste and chemical production, processing, and disposal facilities determines where their pollution will have the greatest impact. The California EPA and Office of Environmental Health Hazard Assessment (OEHHA) actively track the California communities that are most affected by pollution in the [CalEnviroScreen tool](#). These disadvantaged communities experience the highest rates of pollution overall, including waste and chemical-driven pollution. The California Department of Toxic Substances Control (DTSC) found that out of 140 facilities that received universal waste in the state, 83 facilities (59%) were within disadvantaged communities as determined by the CalEnviroScreen study, thereby also exposing them to a disproportionate share of hazardous waste.¹⁶
- Workers in chemical-intensive sectors (e.g. janitorial, beauty (nail and hair salon) construction, agriculture, electronics, transportation, energy, textiles) are subject to disproportionately high exposure to hazardous chemicals, which can lead to chronic illness or death. Certain populations including infants, children, pregnant women, the elderly, and the poor are among the most vulnerable to the adverse effects of chemicals and waste.³

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FURTHER READING

[Identifying Toxic Consumer Products](#)

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CLIMATE CHANGE

Human activity releases greenhouse gases, mainly by burning fossil fuels and degrading the environment.

An increased concentration of these gases in the atmosphere leads to climate change.⁶ In California, the main sectors producing emissions include transportation, industrial processes and manufacturing, agriculture and land-use change, electricity generation, heating and cooking, and the production and disposal of refrigerants.^{1,4,5}

The biosphere has a certain capacity to absorb greenhouse gases, but if we exceed this limit, we risk damaging Earth's life support systems, which we rely on to survive.⁷ Scientists recommend not exceeding a global temperature rise of more than 2 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels. To achieve this, each person can release a maximum of ~1 metric tonne (1,000 kg) of greenhouse gases (GHG) per year.²

The biosphere has a certain capacity to absorb greenhouse gases, but if we exceed this limit, we risk damaging Earth's life support systems, which we rely on to survive.⁷

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PERFORMANCE

1,890% **62%**

Overshoot in GHG per capita

Overshoot in electricity from non-renewable sources

WHAT WE MEASURED

Greenhouse Gas Footprint

- Currently, global average per capita emissions are between 4-5 tonnes. The average American emits around 15 tonnes per year from a territorial perspective and around 23 tonnes per year from a consumption-based perspective.^{4, 8} In some countries, per capita emissions are below 1 tonne per capita.⁹
- According to the Environmental Protection Agency, consumption-based CO₂ equivalent emissions in California were 19.6 tonnes per capita in 2019.¹ The emission inventory from the California Air Resources Board estimates territorial emissions in California to be around 10 tonnes per capita per year.⁵
- Consumption-based inventories subtract emissions associated with exports but include those associated with imports. Often, neither consumption-based nor territorial inventories include emissions associated with international travel or the military.

Renewable Energy

- Apart from reducing energy consumption, another way to reduce our greenhouse gas footprint is to switch from fossil fuels to renewables like wind, solar, and geothermal. Electricity generation accounts for around one third of total energy use.¹⁰ We chose not to include nuclear, biomass, or hydropower due to their environmental impacts.
- Wind, solar, and geothermal made up a combined 38% of California's electricity generation in 2023.³

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- The [Global Warming Solutions Act of 2006](#) (AB 32) and [California Climate Crisis Act](#) of 2022 set a goal of 259 MMT CO₂ eq per year by 2030 and 64.6 MMT CO₂ eq by 2045. This is equal to around 7 tonnes per capita in 2030 and 1.7 tonnes per capita in 2045.^{11, 12}
- The [SB 100 \(2018\) California Renewables Portfolio Standard Program](#) requires that renewable energy supply 100 percent of California's electric retail sales by 2045. This includes sources like nuclear, biomass, and hydro.¹³

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JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

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Renewable and Appropriate Energy
Laboratory (RAEL); Co-Director [Cool
Climate Network](#)

- While some Californians have greenhouse gas footprints well below the state average, wealthy individuals emit 50+ tonnes per year.¹⁴ In the accompanying map, you can see household emissions for different census tracts in the Bay Area.^{15,16}
- Around half the people on Earth do not exceed the per capita limit for CO₂ emissions. Inequality in emission profiles mirrors the inequality of access to wealth and resources both within and between countries.⁹
- In general, countries and locations with the least emissions will be hardest hit by the impacts of climate change. Burning greenhouse gases also produces wealth, so these countries tend to have the least wealth reserves to invest in resilience and recovery from climate impacts.^{17,18}

Map: Greenhouse gas footprint of San Francisco Bay Area households by Census block groups.¹⁶

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FRESHWATER USE

According to the latest research on planetary boundaries, we have transgressed the global limit for sustainable freshwater use.⁴

In California, precipitation is naturally variable, with long cycles of drought followed by shorter, intense wet periods. This hydrological variability is magnified by climate change, which increases the frequency and severity of extreme events (longer droughts, heavier storms). These conditions, combined with overallocated water rights and high water demand from agriculture, urban areas, and ecosystems, create intense competition for water. The California Department of Water Resources (DWR) has a longstanding mandate to monitor statewide water usage, plan for system improvements, and provide guidance on sustainable water management strategies.^{5,6,7} With climate change, water management is only becoming more contentious and high-stakes for communities and ecosystems. The chosen indicators represent two important measures of water use, which together provide a glimpse into the complex, precarious, and highly political freshwater system in California.

Increasingly variable precipitation in California, plus overallocated water rights and high water demand from agriculture, urban areas, and ecosystems, creates intense competition for water.

CONTINUED >>

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FRESHWATER USE

OVERSHOOT

PERFORMANCE

63%

Overshoot in groundwater from basins currently designated as critically overdrafted

76%

Overshoot overshoot in blue water footprint per capita

WHAT WE MEASURED

Groundwater

- Groundwater makes up 40 to 60 percent of California's total water supply, depending on economic and environmental conditions.^A Groundwater storage is declining in many parts of the state, especially in the Central Valley (see graphic). Across the state, 63% of total groundwater is pumped from basins currently designated as critically overdrafted, and annual overdraft from all aquifers is estimated at 2 million acre-feet beyond what is annually regenerated.¹ Overdraft data was determined by measuring groundwater levels between 1998-2018.¹ DWR's forthcoming 2025 Groundwater Update will include data on the sustainable water yields by hydrologic region, which may offer improved groundwater data for future Doughnut assessments.

- A. Includes water for agriculture, urban, and managed wetlands water use only and does not include water for the environment and ecosystem functions.
- B. Water footprint is distinguished by category: blue water (surface and groundwater withdrawals), green water (rainfall stored in soil and used by plants), and gray water (water that has been polluted by human activity).
- C. We calculated the shortfall using percent difference instead of percent change. This method is common when comparing two values equally, without implying one is the starting point.

- Surface water use was considered as another indicator, but we found that precise sustainability thresholds are too difficult to determine. However, data shows that flows in California's two major watersheds, the Bay-Delta and the Colorado Basin, are both highly impaired and likely below the levels necessary to maintain ecosystem integrity.^{8,9} The California Environmental Flows Framework provides regional guidance on environmental flow recommendations in the state, but analysis to date does not consider flow impacts from climate change.¹⁰

Blue Water Footprint

- Blue water footprint^B is a consumption-based indicator that includes total in-state surface and groundwater use, minus water embedded in exported products,^B plus water embedded in imported products. The per-capita water footprint represents the average water use for a Californian, which can be compared with global fair-share and sustainability thresholds.³ Water footprint data was obtained from the U.S. EPA's Environmentally Extended Input Output model V1.0, and indicates that Californians have an annual per capita water footprint of 870.3 cubic meters, 52% above the per capita global sustainable freshwater use threshold of 494 cubic meters.² This per capita threshold was established by dividing the global freshwater use threshold of 4,000 cubic km per year from Steffen et al. (2015) by global population in 2025.^C Other studies have proposed similar per capita freshwater use thresholds and have found similar water footprint numbers in California.^{11, 12}

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- In 2014, [California passed the landmark Sustainable Groundwater Management Act \(SGMA\)](#).¹³ SGMA has shifted significant resources to solve the problem of groundwater overdraft, but challenges persist.¹⁴
- [The Bay-Delta Water Quality Control Plan](#) aims to manage water quality and flow to the Bay-Delta watershed.¹⁵
- In 2023, California added aquifers to the list of natural infrastructure in the Public Resource Code, placing aquifers on par with forests, wetlands, etc. and allowing public funds to replenish aquifers.¹⁶
- In 2024, California signed the [Lower Basin Alternative for the Post-2026 Coordinated Operations of the Colorado River Basin](#), a proposal that reduces California's average Colorado River water allocation by roughly 10% in 2026.^{17,18}

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Benefits of California's water use are not distributed equally; imbalances exist between water use for large-scale agricultural operations and drinking water for residents in water-scarce regions in the Central Valley.¹⁹
- California's antiquated water rights system is based on the dispossession of Indigenous peoples, and continues to operate with stark inequities (learn more with the [California Salmon](#) podcast).²⁰

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Rose Hammock, Pomo, Wailacki, and Maidu. Manager of Community Outreach, Redbud Resource Group.

FURTHER READING

[The California Water Plan Update 2023 Storing Water for the Environment](#)
[California's Water Rights System is Inequitable, Inadequate, and Possibly About to Change](#)

- [California's Fourth Climate Assessment](#) report for Tribal and Indigenous Communities outlines the socio-ecological impacts of dams and impaired waterways across the state, including impacts on salmon populations which are cultural and ecological keystone species.²¹
- There are many other justice and equity issues related to water quality, which we discuss briefly in the [Water Quality and Sanitation section](#).

Map: The Central Valley's agricultural regions contribute to the majority of the state's total annual groundwater overdraft.¹

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LAND-USE CHANGE

California's forests, mountains, grasslands, wetlands, shrublands, and deserts support its unique biodiversity and are fundamental to human wellbeing.

California's forests, mountains, grasslands, wetlands, shrublands, and deserts support its unique biodiversity and are fundamental to human wellbeing. Land provides services which are essential to life, including oxygen, food, and water.⁶ Land is also used for housing, recreation, and transportation, and supplies biomass materials to build modern societies and form the basis for most medicines.⁷

Intact ecosystems on land act as a buffer, absorbing waste and increasing resilience. Globally, forests absorb around 30% of anthropogenic carbon emissions, dampening the impact of climate change.⁶ Over time, the amount and quality of land available to provide critical resources and services has diminished. Today, around 75% of the earth's ice-free land is directly impacted by humans,⁷ with over 40% of land classified as degraded.⁶

In California, land use - mainly agriculture, forestry, and urban development - has had a profound impact on local ecosystems (see table). Both globally and within California, forest cover continues to decrease.^{16,17} The industrial form of agriculture practiced throughout much of California contributes to ecological overshoot in terms of emissions, freshwater use, and the nitrogen and phosphorus flows which lead to eutrophication and acidification.¹⁸

Today, around 75% of the earth's ice-free land is directly impacted by humans,⁷ with over 40% of land classified as degraded.⁶

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OVERSHOOT

LAND-USE CHANGE

PERFORMANCE

28%

Overshoot in land without forest cover

351%

Overshoot in ecological footprint per capita

WHAT WE MEASURED

Forest Cover

Two representative indicators were chosen to assess land-use change. The first focuses on land use within the state of California, while the second looks at how consumption practices in California are impacting land use worldwide.

- Currently around 27% of California is covered with forest, excluding perennial crops. The most recent planetary boundaries assessment sets a boundary of 75% forest cover compared to preindustrial forest baseline levels.¹⁹ Throughout the Holocene, over 50% of California was consistently covered with forest,²⁰ meaning we should aim for at least 37.5% of CA area with forest cover.^A

A. Future work should 1) update the percent forest cover in the Holocene using a dynamic vegetation model and 2) update the boundary of 75% of Holocene forest cover based on the weighted average of boreal, temperate, and tropical forests in California. The first step would likely increase the pre-Holocene baseline forest cover in California up from 50% as this is a minimum estimate, while the second would likely lower the boundary down from 75% due to the forest composition in California compared with the world average (California is mainly temperate forests which have a boundary of 50%).¹⁹ Assuming the baseline forest cover increased by ten percent and the boundary decreased by ten percent, the overshoot percentage would remain relatively consistent.

Table: Land-use change in California

Native vegetation that remains ⁸	<25%
Sierra old-growth forests that remain ⁹	<12%
Coastal redwood old-growth forests that remain ¹⁰	<10%
Wetlands that remain ¹¹	<10%
Land used for agricultural (crops + intensive/extensive grazing) ^{12,13}	≈40%
Farm operations (crops + intensive grazing) ¹⁴	≈24%
Land used for crops ¹	≈9%
Percent organic agriculture ¹⁵	≈9%
Percent developed land ¹	6%

Ecological Footprint

- How much biologically productive area is needed to support the consumption practices of the average Californian? Our demands on nature include food, fiber, and timber, space for roads and other structures, energy production (from hydropower to biomass), and waste absorption. If the per capita ecological footprint exceeds the region's biocapacity, demand for goods and services exceeds what the world's ecosystems can regenerate and assimilate. Ecological footprint is measured by global hectare, which is representative of one hectare of biologically productive land and water, normalized to world average productivity.²¹ We compared California's ecological footprint of 6.68 global hectares per capita to the global biocapacity of 1.48 global hectares per capita.^{4,5}

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- California's Nature-Based Solutions Climate Targets,¹ as required by [Assembly Bill 1757 \(2022\)](#), seek to improve land use management. Policies aimed at 1) reducing wildfire risk through controlled burns and removing vegetation, 2) restoring and conserving wetlands and forests, 3) greening urban areas, 4) increasing to 20% organic agriculture by 2045, ⁵) improving soil health, and ⁶) removing invasive species.

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Over two centuries of expropriation of Indigenous land, inherited wealth disparities, unjust lending practices, and uneven access to support services have produced severe inequities in access to land in California, as in the rest of the United States.²²
- As of 2024, the global average ecological footprint is 2.64 global hectares per capita, while the global biocapacity is 1.48 global hectares.⁵ The Global North has historically contributed and currently contributes much more to this biocapacity deficit than the Global South. If everyone on Earth consumed like the average Californian, we would need more than 4 Earths.⁵

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FURTHER READING

Local: [California's Nature-Based Solutions Climate Targets](#)

Global: [IPCC Special Report on Climate Change and Land](#)

Map: California is losing its trees. Chart: John Blanchard/The Chronicle. Map adaptation courtesy of Jon Wang, lead author of a U.C. Irvine study published in AGU Advances.¹⁷

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NITROGEN & PHOSPHORUS

Synthetic fertilizers and livestock waste are the largest sources of excess nitrogen and phosphorus in the environment.

High levels of nitrogen and phosphorus loading can lead to local water pollution, eutrophication, dead zones, and biodiversity loss. Nitrous oxide (N₂O), a potent greenhouse gas, is also released by agriculture and industry. In 2009, the Planetary Boundaries framework identified thresholds for biogeochemical flows of nitrogen and phosphorus that are already surpassed due to human activity, posing serious risks to ecological stability.⁵ Subsequent research on Planetary Boundaries reaffirms that nitrogen and phosphorus loading is still among the most severely transgressed boundaries.^{6,7}

In California, fertilizers enable the state's enormous agricultural productivity. Yet, roughly half the nitrogen applied every year isn't absorbed by crops and ends up polluting the state's air and water.⁴ To capture global and local environmental impacts, we assessed nitrogen leached in the state as well as consumption-based eutrophication potential. Eutrophication describes how chemical compounds, primarily nitrogen and phosphorus, impact water bodies by stimulating plant growth or algal blooms, leading to oxygen depletion and toxins that can be harmful to humans and other species.⁸

Roughly half the nitrogen applied every year isn't absorbed by crops and ends up polluting California's air and water.¹

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OVERSHOOT

PERFORMANCE

209%

Overshoot in nitrogen leached to groundwater per year

657%

Overshoot in eutrophication potential per capita

WHAT WE MEASURED

Nitrogen Leached

- This indicator is based on research from the Agricultural Sustainability Institute (ASI) at the University of California, Davis. ASI produces a comprehensive accounting of nitrogen at a state level, called the California Nitrogen Assessment.¹ According to this assessment, nearly 380,000 metric tonnes of nitrogen leach into groundwater in California each year.¹ The same study proposes a sustainability threshold of 123,000 metric tonnes based on the amount able to be absorbed by crops, roughly half what is currently leached into the environment.¹ There is uncertainty regarding the specific sustainability threshold for nitrogen, however, it is clear that nitrogen leaching in California is well beyond the boundary to minimize harmful impacts.

Eutrophication Potential

- Eutrophication 'potential' refers to the capacity of chemicals to impact land and water bodies, as opposed to a direct measurement of damages. For this assessment, we use the US EPA's environmentally-extended input-output (USEEIO) model, which measures consumption-based eutrophication potential in each U.S. state (territorial production + import footprint - export footprint). We then downscale to per capita impacts using population data. Various academic articles have proposed planetary boundaries for eutrophication.^{9,10} For this assessment, we use the threshold from Sala et al. 2020 of 29 kg N-eq per capita per year.⁴ According USEEIO data, California's annual per capita Eutrophication Potential is ~220 kg N-eq, over six times beyond the per-capita boundary.³
- The eutrophication potential indicator from EPA's USEEIO model covers marine eutrophication measured in kg nitrogen equivalent (N-eq). Other studies, including Sala et al. 2020, include both marine eutrophication measured in N-eq and a separate indicator for freshwater eutrophication measured phosphorus equivalents (P-eq).⁴ If freshwater eutrophication data for California becomes available, it would be good to include in future assessments.

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Nitrogen Assessment

FURTHER READING

[California Nitrogen Assessment](#)
[Protecting Groundwater Quality
While Replenishing Aquifers](#)

POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- The California State Water Resources Control Board, along with nine Regional Water Quality Control Boards, is responsible for developing and enforcing Total Maximum Daily Loads (TMDLs) for water bodies identified as impaired, as mandated by Section 303(d) of the federal Clean Water Act.¹¹
- The Sustainable Groundwater Management Act (SGMA) of 2014. Although primarily focused on sustainable groundwater use, SGMA mandates that Groundwater Sustainability Agencies (GSAs) also monitor water quality issues related to nutrient loading.¹²

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Nitrogen pollution, particularly nitrates (NO₃) from synthetic fertilizer and livestock manure, disproportionately impact disadvantaged communities in agricultural regions such as the San Joaquin Valley.¹³
- Research shows that California contributes substantially more nutrient loading than its per capita fair share to stay within planetary boundaries, which has implications for global environmental justice.¹⁴

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OCEAN ACIDIFICATION

Ocean health is vital to the stability and habitability of California and the planet.

Increased ocean acidification impacts Earth's oceans in many ways, particularly harming calcifying organisms like shellfish and corals that play a critical role in ocean ecosystems.⁵ Ocean acidification occurs naturally due to upwelling of deep acidic waters into surface water, but has increased dramatically in the past 100 years through the absorption of excess CO₂ in the atmosphere.¹³ If ocean acidification continues at the current rate, ocean ecosystems are expected to deteriorate dramatically.⁵

In California, about 70% of the state's population resides along a coastal ocean area known as the California Current Ecosystem (CCE) that supports a unique variety of life.⁶ The CCE provides many benefits to Californians as a source of food and recreation, and as a carbon sink, but it is at risk of degradation in part due to ocean acidification.²²

The CCE provides many benefits to Californians but it is at risk of degradation in part due to ocean acidification.²²

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OVERSHOOT

PERFORMANCE

91%

Overshoot in pH change

520%

Overshoot in acidification potential footprint per capita

A. Sala et al. 2020 estimate a per capita boundary for ocean acidification in molc H⁺ eq, which can be converted into SO₂-eq as defined by Posch et al. 2008.^{4,9}

WHAT WE MEASURED

Ocean pH

- The global planetary boundary for ocean acidification is set at an average global aragonite saturation of at least 80% of the pre-industrial level ($\Omega_a \geq 2.75$), with the current level at 81% ($\sim 2.8 \Omega_a$), extremely close, but not yet beyond the global ecological limit.² Aragonite saturation, which is essential for marine species and ecosystems (i.e. coral), is used as the control variable for ocean acidification. To regionalize this to California, we used a 2019 study by Osborne et al. that estimated a 0.21 decrease in ocean pH on the California coast compared to pre-industrial levels, whereas the global ocean has seen an average decrease of 0.11.¹ Given global mean aragonite saturation is essentially at the global boundary, this suggests the current reduction in global ocean pH (0.11) is also very near the sustainable boundary and can be used as a reasonable threshold for California. With California's change in ocean acidity almost double (91%) the global average, the state's ocean ecosystems seem to be experiencing acidification

at a much faster rate than the rest of the world, putting them at greater risk of harmful impacts. California's significant overshoot in CO₂-eq emissions per capita (see [Climate Change section](#)) contributes to these global and local rates of ocean acidification.

Acidification Potential

- Sulfur dioxide (SO₂) equivalent, which includes SO₂, ammonia (NH₄), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x), is a common measure of emissions that cause acidification in the environment, often referred to as acidification potential. We recognize that acidification potential relates to terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems more than oceans, but is nonetheless an important and related environmental indicator. Common anthropogenic sources of these pollutants include fossil-fuel combustion (especially coal), industrial processes, and agriculture (fertilizers and livestock manure). SO₂-eq footprint is a consumption-based measure assessing total in-state SO₂-eq generated, minus SO₂-eq in exported products, plus SO₂-eq in imported products. According to the U.S. EPA's Environmentally Extended Input Output state model, the average Californian has an annual SO₂-eq footprint of 28.5 kg.³ Compared to the global sustainable threshold of 4.6 kg per capita, Californians are overshooting this boundary by more than 500%.^{A,4}

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SOCIAL COHESION

WATER & SANITATION

ECOLOGICAL CEILING

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BIODIVERSITY LOSS

CHEMICAL POLLUTION

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LAND-USE CHANGE

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Additional indicators considered

- Ongoing work on the impact of land-based nutrient inputs on the availability of aerobic and calcifying habitat for key pelagic taxa (such as pteropods, decapods, kelp canopies) in California has found that sublethal, ecologically relevant changes are pervasive.^{18,21} Pteropod shell dissolution is a biological indicator of ocean acidification.¹⁰ A 2023 study found that up to 40% of pteropods within the California Current Ecosystem are affected by dissolution.¹¹
- Aquatic deoxygenation (hypoxia) is an additional indicator of global freshwater and marine ecosystem health.¹² Hypoxia makes it difficult or impossible for aquatic organisms to survive and can cause dead zones where minimal ocean life is present. Hypoxia occurs naturally but has increased in frequency and scale due to human impacts.
- Research on thresholds can provide the foundation for consistent marine vulnerability assessments and evaluation of ocean management strategies.^{19,20} The planetary boundary for Ocean Acidification is under review to be tightened, leading to a greater boundary overshoot.²³

Figure: Ocean acidification - conceptual diagram of the state of carbonates in the oceans under the higher-acid conditions expected for the year 2100.

Source: <https://www.britannica.com/science/ocean-acidification>⁸

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- CA [AB 2139 \(2016\) Ocean Protection Council: ocean acidification and hypoxia](#) mandated the Ocean Protection Council to establish an Ocean Acidification and Hypoxia science task force within California to address the concern of ocean acidification and contributed to the development of the [California Ocean Acidification Action Plan](#).^{13,7} This plan details targeted actions to reduce and prepare for the impacts of ocean acidification in the state.⁷
- CA [SB 1363 \(2016\) Ocean Protection Council: Ocean Acidification and Hypoxia Reduction Program](#) required the Ocean Protection Council to coordinate ocean protection and regulation in the state and created the Ocean Acidification and Hypoxia Reduction Program to take specific actions to mitigate and prevent ocean acidification.¹⁴

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Communities which depend upon the ocean for its economic and social benefits will be the most impacted by changes in marine ecosystems. Globally, about 50% percent of people in the least developed countries rely on fish as their primary source of protein, leaving them vulnerable to changes in fish populations as a result of ocean acidification.¹⁵ On the West Coast of the US, including California, numerous communities scoring high on the community social vulnerability index also show significant commercial fishing reliance, particularly in Northern California, Oregon and Washington.¹⁶

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OZONE DEPLETION

The ozone layer protects all life on Earth by absorbing ultraviolet radiation produced by the Sun before it reaches Earth's surface.

It prevents adverse health and environmental impacts, such as increased rates of skin cancer, cataracts, and ecosystem damage.³ Beginning in the mid-20th century certain chemicals now known as ozone-depleting substances (ODSs, including chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs)) began to be manufactured in large quantities for industrial and consumer use. Triggered by UV light, these chemicals cause catalytic reactions that deplete stratospheric ozone.³

The international Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer established phase-out schedules for ODS production and consumption. 197 countries, including the United States, have signed onto the Montreal Protocol and successfully reversed the global trends in ozone layer depletion through the phaseout of ODSs.⁸ The protocol is enforced in California by the US EPA through the Clean Air Act Title VI.⁴ The Kigali Amendment to the protocol added phase-out schedules for HFCs, which are used in many applications to replace ODSs, due to their potency as greenhouse gases.⁵

Current emissions represent an over 80% reduction since 2000 and demonstrate the state's commitment to phase out ozone-depleting substance.²

DATA SNAPSHOT

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- NITROGEN & PHOSPHORUS
- OCEAN ACIDIFICATION
- OZONE DEPLETION**

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OZONE DEPLETION

OVERSHOOT

PERFORMANCE

0%

Overshoot of Montreal Protocol compliance

0%

Overshoot in lack of ozone layer thickness

WHAT WE MEASURED

Compliance with the Montreal Protocol on Ozone-Depleting Substances

- The California Air Resources Board (CARB) monitors and reports on ODS emissions in the state and in 2022 estimated 9.6 MMTCO₂e (million metric tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent) of ODSs were emitted.^{2, A} These current emissions represent an over 80% reduction since 2000 and demonstrate the state's commitment to phase out ODSs. While the protocol mandates a phase-out of the production and consumption of ODSs, emissions are a useful measurement to monitor the overall impact of the state on the ozone layer. CARB also manages a compliance offset protocol for the capture and destruction of ozone-depleting substances produced in the state.¹

Ozone Layer Thickness

- Global average thickness of the ozone layer measures the concentration of ozone molecules in the atmosphere across the planet. Under the Montreal Protocol, an international Scientific Assessment Panel publishes quadrennial reports on the health of the ozone layer and global production of ODSs. In 2020, the global average thickness of the ozone layer was reported at about 284 Dobson units (DU).³ The planetary boundaries framework estimates the global threshold at a <5% reduction from the preindustrial level of 290 DU (no less than 276 DU), which places the 2022 global average within the boundary.⁶

A. We focused on ODS only here. While ODS substitutes do not affect ozone depletion directly, they can have high Global Warming Potentials.⁷

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OZONE DEPLETION

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POLICY SPOTLIGHT

- The [US Clean Air Act Title VI](#) of 1990 established limits on the production and import of ODS and authorized the EPA to create and enforce an ODS phaseout plan.
- CA [SB 605](#) of 2014 directed CARB to develop a comprehensive strategy to reduce HFC emissions, and [SB 1383](#) of 2016 directed CARB to approve and begin implementing this strategy. SB 1383 also established a target to reduce HFC emissions by 40% below 2013 levels by 2030.

JUSTICE SPOTLIGHT

- Depletion of the ozone layer impacts all people across the globe. However, production and consumption of ODSs have historically occurred primarily in developed countries. In recognition of this, the Montreal Protocol established different phaseout timelines for developed and developing countries, with more time allotted to developing countries with low rates of ODS consumption.⁷ The Montreal protocol also established a multilateral fund to provide financial assistance for developing countries to meet the phaseout requirements.⁷ Additionally, it established committees and panels ([MCTOC](#), [MBTOC](#), [TEAP](#)) which provide assistance and technical expertise on phasing out ODSs and introducing newer compounds.

Figure: [California Trends in ODS and ODS Substitutes Emissions](#).²

DATA DETAILS FOR SOCIAL INDICATORS

SOCIAL THRESHOLD	ABBREVIATION	INDICATOR AND UNIT	CALIFORNIA	DESIRABLE	SHORTFALL	YEAR (MEASURED)
CONNECTIVITY & TRANSPORTATION	Internet Access	1. Percent of households without any internet subscription or access through cellphone-only	16.9%	0%	16.9%	2023
	Transit Report Card	2. Report card scores on vehicle miles traveled and transit access only	6	10	40%	2021
EDUCATION	Literacy Rate	1. Percent of people over 16-74 with literacy proficiency at or below Level 1	28%	0%	28%	2017
	Student Loan Debt	2. Percent of college graduates with student loan debt	46%	0%	46%	2020
ENERGY	Energy Burden	1. Percent of households whose energy bill was $\geq 10\%$ of household income	19.6%	0%	19.6%	2022
	Energy Reliability	2. Percent of population living in counties with average total outage time of 6 hours or more, per year	7%	0%	7%	2023
EQUITY	Racial Equity Index	1. Inclusion score based on racial gaps in economic vitality, readiness, and connectedness	60	100	40%	2023
	Gender Pay Gap	2. Percent of men's median wage earned by women for full-time, year-round work	87.1%	100%	12.9%	2023
FOOD	Food Insecurity	1. Percent of households who live with food insecurity	11.4%	0%	11.4%	2023
	Vegetables Per Day	2. Percent of adults who eat ≥ 1 serving(s) of vegetables per day	59.2%	100%	40.8%	2022
HEALTH	Life Expectancy	1. Percent of population living in counties with life expectancy below OECD average (80.9 years)	32.5%	0%	32.5%	2023
	Healthcare Affordability	2. Percent of adults who delayed, skipped, or reduced their utilization of health care due to costs	53%	0%	53%	2023
HOUSING	Homelessness	1. Point-in-time count of unhoused people	0.47%	0%	35.9%	2024
	Housing Cost Burden	2. Percent of renters with housing costs that exceed 30% of household income	55%	0%	55%	2018
INCOME & WORK	Poverty	1. Percent of people experiencing poverty defined by supplemental poverty rate (3-year average)	15.4%	0%	15.4%	2021-2023
	Unemployment (U6)	2. Percent of unemployed people, including workers employed part-time for economic reasons, and those marginally attached to the labor force	9.3%	0%	9.3%	2023
PEACE & JUSTICE	Violent Crime	1. Percent of people living in counties with a violent crime rate above 200 incidents per 100,000 residents	99.9%	0%	99.9%	2023
	Police Scorecard	2. Averaged score for police funding, accountability, violence, and approach to law enforcement	35%	100%	65%	2023
POLITICAL VOICE	Voter Turnout	1. Percent of eligible voter turnout	60%	100%	40%	2024
	Registered Voters	2. Percent of eligible voters who are not registered to vote	16%	0%	16%	2024
SOCIAL COHESION	Income Inequality	1. Percent of people living in counties with a Gini Index below 0.30	0%	100%	100%	2023
	Report Not Happy	2. Percent of people who report they are "not too happy"	26%	0%	26%	2023
WATER & SANITATION	Water Quality	1. Percent of people who receive water from systems that do not meet water quality standards	2.2%	0%	2.2%	2025
	Sanitation Access	2. Percent of people who lack basic access to sanitation	0.6%	0%	0.6%	2019

DATA DETAILS FOR ECOLOGICAL INDICATORS

ECOLOGICAL CEILING	ABBREVIATION	INDICATOR: LOCAL/TERRITORIAL GLOBAL/CONSUMPTION	UNIT	CALIFORNIA	DESIRABLE	OVERSHOOT	YEAR (MEASURED)
AIR POLLUTION	Particulate Matter	1. Percent of air basins in violation of annual average national PM _{2.5} standard (9 µg/m ³)	%	60%	0%	60%	2023
	Ozone Pollution	2. Percent of air basins in violation of the national ozone standard of 0.070 ppm	%	60%	0%	60%	2023
BIODIVERSITY LOSS	Protected Area	1. Percent protected land / sea area	%	25.2% / 16.2%	50% / 50%	50% / 68% (average = 59%)	2024
	At-Risk Species	2. Percent of animal / plant species at risk of extinction	%	33.1% / 29.7%	3%	1003% / 890% (average = 947%)	2022
CHEMICAL POLLUTION	Toxic Pesticides Applied	1. Percent of total pesticides applied per year which are categorized as high-risk toxins	%	65%	0%	65%	2022
	Toxic Chemicals Released	2. Percent of toxic chemicals released out of total toxic chemicals produced per year	%	13%	0%	13%	2023
CLIMATE CHANGE	Greenhouse Gas Footprint	1. Greenhouse gas footprint per capita (consumption)	Tonnes CO ₂ eq	19.6	0.985	1890%	2019
	Renewable Electricity	2. Percent of electricity from renewables (solar, wind, and geothermal)	%	38%	100%	62%	2023
FRESHWATER USE	Groundwater	1. Percent of groundwater pumped from basins currently designated as critically overdrafted	%	63%	0%	63%	2014
	Blue Water Footprint	2. Blue water footprint per capita	Cubic Meters H ₂ O	870.3	494	76%	2020
LAND USE CHANGE	Forest Cover	1. Percent of land with forest cover	%	27%	37.5%	28%	2022
	Ecological Footprint	2. Ecological footprint per capita	Global Hectares	6.68	1.48	351%	2014
NITROGEN & PHOSPHORUS	Nitrogen Leached	1. Nitrogen leached to groundwater per year	Tonnes Nitrogen	380,000	123,000	209%	2005
	Eutrophication Potential	2. Eutrophication potential footprint per capita	Kg N eq	219.6	29	657%	2020
OCEAN ACIDIFICATION	Ocean pH	1. Change in pH compared to preindustrial levels	pH	0.21	<0.11	91%	2015
	SO ₂ Footprint	2. Acidification potential footprint per capita	Kg SO ₂ eq	28.5	4.6	520%	2020
OZONE DEPLETION	Ozone-Depleting Substances	1. Compliance with Montreal Protocol on Ozone-Depleting Substances	Yes/No	Yes	Yes	No Overshoot	2014
	Ozone Layer	2. Global average thickness of ozone layer	Dobson Units	284	>276	No Overshoot	2020

FOR MORE DETAILS, YOU CAN EXPLORE THE [INDICATOR SPREADSHEET HERE](#)

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SOCIAL FOUNDATION

CONNECTIVITY AND TRANSPORTATION

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ECOLOGICAL CEILING

AIR POLLUTION

Indicator 1: Particulate Matter

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Indicator 2: Ozone Pollution

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CHEMICAL POLLUTION

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CLIMATE CHANGE

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